

**IZMIR UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
AEROSPACE ENGINEERING**

FENG 498 PROJECT REPORT

**Trajectory design and flight dynamics from near-Earth departure
to very Low altitude flybys of Phobos by a solar sail-propelled
SmallSat orbiting Mars**

Authors: Özge Öztürk

Supervisor: Dr. Fabrizio Pinto

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15631174>

Contents

1	Introduction	7
1.1	Problem Statement	7
1.2	Motivation	7
2	Literature Survey	8
2.1	Battin, Richard A., "An Introduction To The Mathematics and Methods of Astrodynamics"	8
2.2	Arfken, George B., "Mathematical Methods for Physicists"	9
2.3	L. Johnson et al., "Solar sail propulsion for interplanetary cubesats"	9
2.4	Y. Guo et al., "The earth-mars transfer trajectory optimization of solar sail based on hp-Adaptive pseudospectral method"	10
2.5	O. Mori et al., "First Solar Power Sail Demonstration by IKAROS"	11
2.6	D. Spencer et al., "The LightSail 2 solar sailing technology demonstration"	11
2.7	A. Sobey, T. R. Lockett, "Design and Development of NEA Scout Solar Sail Deployer Mechanism"	12
2.8	G. L. Matloff et al., "Phobos/Deimos Sample Return via Solar Sail"	12
2.9	C. Zengin et al., "Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting Mars and its moons"	13
2.10	E. Joffre et al., "Trajectory design and guidance for landing on Phobos"	13
3	Methodology	14
3.1	Mission Plan	15
3.2	Trajectory Design by NASA GMAT	15
3.2.1	Implementing Martian Moons	16
3.2.2	Reference Frames in NASA GMAT	18
3.2.3	Sphere of Influence of Martian Moons'	22
3.2.4	NASA GMAT 2025a	23
3.3	Phobos Flyby	24
3.3.1	Gravitational Field of Phobos	24
3.3.2	Spherical Model SPAD File	25
3.4	Aerobraking	26
3.4.1	Martian Atmosphere	27
3.4.2	Aerobraking Maneuver	27
3.4.3	Sensitivity Analysis	29
4	Results and Discussion	31
4.1	Using NASA GMAT 2025a	31
4.2	Gravitational Field of Phobos and Flyby	32
4.3	SRP Modeling by SPAD	32

4.4	Aerobraking in Martian Atmosphere	33
5	Conclusions	34
5.1	Future Improvements	35
6	Acknowledgements	35
A	Appendix	39
A.1	Multibody ForceModel Definition in NASA GMAT 2025a for Phobos Flyby	39
A.2	NASA GMAT 2025a Phobos Flyby Script	39
A.3	NASA GMAT 2025a Phobos Flyby Script With SPAD	57
A.4	Aerobraking in the Martian Atmosphere	74

Abstract

From their discovery in 1877, Mars and its moons have always been a center of attention in astronomical studies. And yet, the dynamics of operating in the Martian system remain unexplored. This project aims to improve the precision of the trajectory of a SmallSat class solar sail-propelled satellite by using advanced trajectory design simulations. The main objective of the study is to understand the gravitational perturbations on the trajectory of a satellite caused by the Phobos' gravitational field. The modeling of the solar radiation pressure applied on the spacecraft is studied for further improvements. The [SPAD](#) file for the spherical model for the solar radiation pressure is compared to the default implementations. Furthermore, [Aerobraking](#) by using Martian atmosphere is investigated. The results and future implementation suggestions are shared and commented upon.

List of Symbols

Aerobraking A method to slow down a solar sail-propelled spacecrafts by exposing the solar sail to atmospheric drag.

ECC Eccentricity, the ellipticity of an orbit. Obtained by dividing the difference between the apoapsis difference and periapsis difference divided by the sum of them. 0 indicates perfect circle and shifts to hyperbola as grows larger than 1.

Epoch A specific point in time used as a reference point in measuring or defining quantities.

RMAG The magnitude of the distance of the center of mass of a body from the origin of the reference frame in NASA GMAT.

NASA GMAT NASA General Mission Analysis Tool, an open source advanced simulation tool developed by NASA.

SMA Semi-major axis, half the longest diameter of an elliptical orbit.

SPAD Solar Pressure and Aerodynamic Drag, a special formatted file that includes the data about the effective solar radiation pressure and aerodynamic drag on a spacecraft, obtained from advanced simulation programmes or wind tunnel tests.

SPICE Kernel file format from NASA NAIF that contains planetary ephemerides, built-in NASA GMAT.

SPK Kernel file format from NAIF that contains planetary ephemerides, obtained from NASA NAIF Planetary Data System.

SRP Solar Radiation Pressure, the pressure due to the force exerted by photons on a surface due to the momentum carried by electromagnetic radiation.

SOI Sphere of Influence, the conceptual sphere which indicates the outer edge where the gravitational field of the smaller object outpowers the gravitational field of the bigger object.

ρ When calculating Sphere of Influence, the semi-major axis of the smaller celestial body around the bigger one.

1 Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

Interplanetary missions face significant challenges in navigating complex gravitational environments and achieving precise trajectory control. One of the main issues in these challenges is the propulsion mechanism of the spacecraft. Solar sailing offers a way to travel long distances, but it introduces new problems. The motion of a solar sail is affected by many forces, including gravity from planets and moons, and radiation pressure from the Sun. Some of the main challenges are calculating gravitational perturbations from celestial bodies, precise sail attitude control, and the limitations of simulation tools in modeling these dynamics with sufficient accuracy.

Current approaches often rely on simplified dynamical models and drag approximations. This causes inaccuracies that can significantly impact mission success, particularly during critical phases such as Mars orbit insertion and close flybys to Phobos. Furthermore, existing simulations may neglect the realistic sail dynamics and atmospheric drag modeling.

This project focuses on building a more accurate simulation of a solar sail mission to Mars and Phobos. By enhancing NASA GMAT simulations with high-fidelity gravity models and realistic SPAD files, the study aims to enhance the accuracy of trajectory planning and mission design for solar sail-propelled CubeSats. This designed mission is expected to contribute to the literature about the possible fields of use of solar sail-propelled systems.

1.2 Motivation

Solar sails produce thrust by collecting solar radiation from their solar panels, making them highly suitable for small satellites. As interest in cost-effective exploration of Mars and its moons grows, solar sails present a solution for achieving extended science campaigns with minimal propulsion requirements.

Phobos, due to its low altitude and irregular gravity field, presents both scientific value and navigational complexity. Very low altitude flybys require precise trajectory design and advanced dynamic

modeling. Existing tools often rely on simplified assumptions that do not account for key factors such as non-uniform gravity, solar radiation pressure dynamics, or realistic atmospheric drag during Mars aerobraking.

This project addresses these limitations by integrating high-fidelity gravitational models, SPAD-based solar sail dynamics, and realistic Martian atmospheric effects into NASA GMAT. The resulting simulation will provide more accurate trajectory prediction and mission planning. By demonstrating the feasibility of a solar sail-propelled SmallSat performing controlled flybys of Phobos after aerobraking by the Martian atmosphere, this work aims to contribute directly to the future of low-cost, autonomous deep space exploration and supports the development of advanced guidance and navigation strategies for multi-body environments.

2 Literature Survey

2.1 Battin, Richard A., "An Introduction To The Mathematics and Methods of Astrodynamics"

Sphere of Influence (SOI) defines the region around an object that the gravitational field of the centered object dominates over the gravitational field of nearby objects. Battin, Richard A. [1] explains Sphere of Influence of a celestial body and denotes the Eq.1 to calculate the radius of the Sphere of Influence.

$$r_{\text{SOI}} = \left(\frac{k_{\text{Phobos}}}{k_{\text{Mars}}} \right)^{\frac{2}{5}} \rho \quad (1)$$

This formula indicates at what distance the gravitational field of Phobos dominates the gravitational field of Mars and becomes more effective on the spacecraft. The figure ρ denotes the semi-major axis of the smaller celestial body around the bigger one.

2.2 Arfken, George B., "Mathematical Methods for Physicists"

In Mathematical Methods for Physicists, Arfken, George B. [2] explains the gravity fields with the example of Earth's gravitational field. In this book, it is shown that the gravitational coefficients can be written in the form of Laplace Series over the Earth, the Moon and Mars examples (Eq.2).

$$U(r, \theta, \phi) = GMR \left[\frac{R}{r} - \sum_{\ell=2}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\ell} \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^{\ell+1} [C_{\ell m} Y_{\ell m}^e(\theta, \phi) + S_{\ell m} Y_{\ell m}^o(\theta, \phi)] \right] \quad (2)$$

Where $Y_{\ell m}^e(\theta, \phi)$ and $Y_{\ell m}^o(\theta, \phi)$ are defined as:

$$Y_{\ell m}^e(\theta, \phi) = P_{\ell}^m(\cos \theta) \cos(m\phi) \quad (3)$$

$$Y_{\ell m}^o(\theta, \phi) = P_{\ell}^m(\cos \theta) \sin(m\phi) \quad (4)$$

The significance of understanding gravitational coefficients is, it is essential in implementing the gravitational coefficients in NASA GMAT simulation. The effect of the gravitational coefficients will be investigated in the simulations.

2.3 L. Johnson et al., "Solar sail propulsion for interplanetary cubesats"

Solar sail propulsion is a method of producing thrust and propagating in space by reflecting solar photons coming from the Sun with a large sail made of highly reflective and light material. [3] The photon pressure provided from the Sun results in high Δv values in long term deep space missions. This makes solar sailing relatively more cost-effective compared to the chemical or electrical propulsion systems. L. Johnson et al. states that the solar sail propulsion will increase the feasibility of space exploration and enable missions that currently are not feasible.

2.4 Y. Guo et al., "The earth-mars transfer trajectory optimization of solar sail based on hp-Adaptive pseudospectral method"

Unlike traditional propulsion systems that rely on chemical fuels, solar sails provide continuous and propellantless thrust by solar radiation pressure (SRP). Even though the SRP is extremely weak, the continuous effect of this pressure on the solar sail produces acceleration sufficient enough for the spacecraft to propagate in interplanetary space. [4] The consistent increase in the velocity of the spacecraft may result in five to seven times the velocity of the current fastest spacecraft, which makes solar sailing an optimal method for long-term deep space missions. Even though solar sailing is a relatively new technology, its advantages and promising experiment results have made solar sailing a focus of research activities.

One of the key points in designing a solar sail mission is optimizing the trajectory since it significantly increases the functionality of the spacecraft. An efficient implementation of a solar sail requires nonlinear dynamic optimal control with state and control constraints which is very not easy to handle. This is one of the reasons why solar sailing technologies are in early research stage. Further research and experiments are needed to verify how solar sail propelled systems work.

The solar radiation pressure occurs as a result of the momentum exchange between photons coming from the Sun and the solar sail of the spacecraft. There are two orthogonal components of the solar radiation pressure: the radial component (Eq. 5) which effects the orbit shape and the tangential component Eq.(6) which is contributing to the orbital energy.

$$F_r = P_s A_\varepsilon (\cos \alpha_n - \sin \alpha_t) \quad (5)$$

$$F_t = P_s A_\varepsilon (\cos \alpha_n + \sin \alpha_t) \quad (6)$$

Where the P_s is the SRP and A_ε is the effective area facing the Sun, $A_\varepsilon = A \cos \alpha$, α being the pitch angle. The α is the angle between unit normal vector \mathbf{n} and unit normal vector of incident rays \mathbf{r} . By this

geometrical definitions, the resulting SRP acting on the solar sail can be defined as Eq.7.

$$F_s = F_i + F_t = 2P_s A \cos^2 \alpha_n = 2P_s A (\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 \mathbf{n} \quad (7)$$

2.5 O. Mori et al., "First Solar Power Sail Demonstration by IKAROS"

In 2010, Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) launched IKAROS (Interplanetary Kite-craft Accelerated by the Radiation Of the Sun) and performed the first successful interplanetary mission with a solar sail of 196 m². IKAROS mission aimed to make contact with the Trojan Asteroids near Jupiter for the first time by using thin film solar power generation and world's first hybrid ion/photon propulsion. [5] Other technological advancements in solar sailing such as deployment of a large sail and navigation control have been displayed in this pioneering mission. The spacecraft successfully completing the first interplanetary flight showed the significance of solar sailing in deepspace missions and proved that the solar sailing is a promising technology as a way of propagating in space.

2.6 D. Spencer et al., "The LightSail 2 solar sailing technology demonstration"

The LightSail program by The Planetary Society was started in 2009 to advance solar sailing technology. LightSail 1 was launched in 2015 in order to test the deployment sequence and or-orbit operations of the CubeSat. The LightSail 1 successfully deployed its sail and provided many experimental data alongside the pre-launch tests, which enhanced the development of LightSail 2. The LightSail 1 did not have attitude control features in mission objective. In 2019, LightSail 2 was launched to the Earth orbit with the main mission objective of practicing attitude control with respect to the Sun. The LightSail 2 successfully deployed a 32 m² solar sail, achieved the goal of controlling the orientation of the solar sails and transferring the obtained data to ground. [6]

The sail control algorithm consists of a cycle of "On-Off" attitudes switching twice per the orbit. The "On" attitude maximizes the solar radiation pressure by keeping the normal vector of the sail pointing towards the direction the sail is moving, which is away from the Sun. The "Off" attitude minimizes the

thrust by aligning the solar sail normal vector and the solar radiation from the Sun as perpendicular to each other. The switch between these two attitudes occur twice per orbit, when the solar sail is closest and the furthest from the Sun. By practising attitude control and achieving the goals that are aimed in mission objectives, the LightSail 2 mission enabled a significant development in the solar sailing technology.

2.7 A. Sobey, T. R. Lockett, "Design and Development of NEA Scout Solar Sail Deployer Mechanism"

The SmallSat class satellite Near Earth Asteroid (NEA) Scout was launched by NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) to perform the task of imaging and characterizing a Near Earth Asteroid. The mission plan was the 14 kg CubeSat would propagate with a 86 m² sail for 2.5 years to reach the targeted asteroid. The development of this mission significantly contributed to developing solar sail design, especially on systems that are deploying the solar sail. [7] Unfortunately, the communication with the spacecraft could not be established and the spacecraft was lost. However, the lessons learned from this mission will be used in order to develop solar sailing technologies for future missions and deepspace discoveries.

2.8 G. L. Matloff et al., "Phobos/Deimos Sample Return via Solar Sail"

In 2004, an early feasibility study by Matloff et al. [8] showed quantitatively that it is possible to perform a sample return mission to the Martian moons by using a solar sail as the means of propulsion (see also: Ref. [9]). This study centers a sample return mission which uses solar sailing as the propulsion system after escaping the Earth. The proposed spacecraft that was used in the approximations had a total mass of 218 kg and sail radius of 50 m.

The spacecraft is planned to enter the Martian system by aerobraking. The feasibility analysis of aerobraking maneuvers indicated that the maneuver is possible with the spacecraft closing to the planet by 120 km at most. The thermal analysis were indicating this mission is quantitatively possible. The total mission is planned to last for 4.71 years including the rendezvous with both Martian moons, Phobos and

Deimos, and coming back to the Earth. This quantitative study on feasibility of Martian moon rendezvous and aerobraking by the Martian atmosphere are investigated by trajectory simulation tools in the present study.

2.9 C. Zengin et al., "Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting Mars and its moons"

Solar Radiation and Aerodynamic Drag (**SPAD**) files include the properties of a spacecraft. **NASA GMAT** requires **SPAD** files in order to calculate the **SRP** acting on a spacecraft in a realistic manner. Using an **SPAD** file is proven to result in a more stable outcome by Zengin et al. [10] in the study they conducted. **SPAD** file of a spacecraft is implemented by wind tunnel tests or advanced simulation tools. The trajectory simulation tool **NASA GMAT** uses the cannonball approximation in calculating the SRP by default, when user does not provide a **SPAD** file. In the simulations designed by Zengin et al., the researchers compared the results of the **NASA GMAT** simulations of the default solar radiation model cannonball approximation with the **SPAD** file that implements cannonball approximation for simplicity. It has been observed that the simulation which uses the **SPAD** file gave a more stable result for **ECC** (eccentricity) and **SMA** (semimajor axis) values. The **SPAD** file implementation may provide a more realistic approach and enhance the accuracy of the trajectory design. In the present study, the **SPAD** file of the cannonball approximation will be implemented to obtain a more realistic trajectory design.

2.10 E. Joffre et al., "Trajectory design and guidance for landing on Phobos"

This study by Airbus Defence and Space and the University of Bristol centers the mission design and control of a sample return mission to Phobos. Even though the proposed propulsion system is not explicitly mentioned in the study, the sample return systems must inherit chemical propulsion systems. As sample return mission requires landing on Phobos, the gravitational effects of the Martian moon is considered.

Phobos has a highly complex and uncertain dynamics environment. [13] Due to its irregular shape non-homogenous mass distribution, the Gravity Harmonics Coefficients $C_{n,m}$ and $S_{n,m}$ of the moon

are represented by Lagrangian Points. Phobos inherits a non-spherical gravitational field. Alongside with Phobos' elliptic orbit around Mars, these properties form the main reasons of perturbations in the Mars-Phobos system.

Phobos' revolution around Mars is synchronous with its axial spin. This makes Phobos "tidally locked" to Mars, similar to the case with Earth and the Moon, always the same side of the moon is visible from the planet. The libration differs between 0.3 and 1.90 degrees over a period of 2.26 terrestrial years. [13] Since the tidal effects of Mars are too slow to be significantly effective on the short term mission plan, therefore can be neglected. In the present study, a similar approach will be followed and perturbations caused by the tidal effects of Mars will be neglected.

3 Methodology

The trajectory of the solar sail is carefully implemented. In this implementation, the aim was to reach the most realistic mission design by considering forces such as gravitational perturbations caused by Phobos, the drag force from a realistic atmospheric model of Mars and solar radiation pressure by using advanced simulation tools. The properties of the proposed spacecraft are given in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The Proposed Solar Sail

3.1 Mission Plan

The mission starts off from 72044461.4 kilometers distance from the Earth, where the solar sail is inserted in heliocentric orbit. The solar sail completes several orbits around the Sun by having a periapsis closer to the Sun in each orbit. By this method, the solar sails are subjected to immense amount of force from solar radiation pressure, which carry the spacecraft to a further apoapsis in each orbit. This maneuver is referred as "Sundiver" maneuver and it is a popular way to implement interplanetary missions with solar sails. In 2020, Tang et al. studied that the Sundiver approach takes twice long as the direct transfer to the Martian orbit. [14] (see also: Ref. [15]) However, the aim of this mission is to enhance the solar sailing technologies by collecting on-mission data. Therefore, mission length does not cause any disadvantage in the present study.

After reaching to the Martian system, the spacecraft rendezvous with Phobos. The spacecraft flies close to Phobos for a fraction of a time. To enter the Martian system orbit, the spacecraft uses the drag force from Martian atmosphere to aerobrake. The spacecraft is expected to enter the orbit of Mars in an altitude close to Phobos to make deeper analysis on the Martian moon. The aerobrake maneuver concludes the mission plan of this study.

3.2 Trajectory Design by NASA GMAT

The trajectory design of the solar sail has been investigated by using the NASA General Mission Analysis Tool ([NASA GMAT](#)). [NASA GMAT](#) is a Free Open Source Software (FOSS) developed by NASA, with the main objective of space mission design, optimization, and navigation. The advanced features and high computational capabilities of [NASA GMAT](#) make it an optimal tool for trajectory design.

To implement the trajectory of the mission investigated in this study, some adjustments have been made in [NASA GMAT](#).

3.2.1 Implementing Martian Moons

Martian moons are not included in the default version of [NASA GMAT](#). Therefore, the moons, Phobos and Deimos, were inserted before starting the mission simulation. To implement Martian moons, navigate to Resources > SolarSystem > Mars. By right clicking on Mars, navigate to Add > Moon. After entering the name of the moon, the standard gravitational parameter (Mu), equatorial radius and flattening of the moons are inserted in the Properties tab shown in Fig.2. In th Orbit tab shown in Fig.3, NAIF ID and [SPK](#) files are inserted. The [SPK](#) file provided for both moons are the same. The mar085.bsp kernel file obtained from NASA NAIF Planetary Data System [20] is inserted in for both Phobos and Deimos. Texture and 3D model can be inserted in the Visualization tab upon request. After all implementations are completed, the Apply and OK buttons are clicked respectively.

Figure 2: The Properties Tab for Deimos

Figure 3: The Orbit Tab for Phobos

The parameters inserted in both Properties and Orbit tabs of Phobos and Deimos are given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Table 1: Phobos Parameters

Parameter	Value
Mu	$0.00070934 \frac{\text{km}^3}{\text{s}^2}$
Equatorial Radius	13.5 km
Flattening	0.3185185185185186
NAIF ID	401

Table 2: Deimos Parameters

Parameter	Value
Mu	$0.000158817 \frac{\text{km}^3}{\text{s}^2}$
Equatorial Radius	7.5 km
Flattening	0.3066666666666666
NAIF ID	402

This concludes the insertion of the moons.

3.2.2 Reference Frames in NASA GMAT

A reference frame is a coordinate system defined for a specific origin and orientation. Newtonian forces require inertial (not accelerating) reference frames to be defined and measured correctly. As the motion is relative, the correct reference frame should be used in the definition of the vector quantities. The correct reference frame definition is crucial in measuring the parameters accurately and designing a successful mission.

There are total of 20 different coordinate system in [NASA GMAT](#) that can be used in defining reference frames. [16] The most common ones, MJ2000Eq and MJ2000Ec, and more specific ones, BodyFixed and BodyInertial, are investigated to understand how does [NASA GMAT](#) define reference frames. Experiments were conducted to show how does different coordinate system options effect the result for vector quantities.

MJ2000Eq

MJ2000Eq is the coordinate system which is used as the default reference frame in [NASA GMAT](#). It centers the planet given by the user as the origin of the reference frame, based on [Epoch J2000](#) (January 1, 2000, 12:00 TT). The z-axis is normal to the planet's mean equator at the [Epoch](#) time.

MJ2000Ec

MJ2000Ec is another commonly used coordinate system. It centers the planet given by the user as the origin of the reference frame, based on [Epoch J2000](#) (January 1, 2000, 12:00 TT), as in MJ200Eq. The z-axis is normal to the planet's mean ecliptic at the [Epoch](#) time.

BodyFixed

The BodyFixed is a non-inertial coordinate system which centers a body, a planet or a spacecraft, at the origin. This coordinate system references to the body equator and the prime meridian of the body. The main purpose of this coordinate system is to always keep the body in the center and in the initial orientation, no matter how the body propagates or rotates.

BodyInertial

The BodyInertial reference centers a celestial body at the origin. The z-axis is aligned with the spin axis of the body at the [Epoch](#) of J2000 (January 1, 2000, 12:00 TT). This inertial reference frame does not rotate with the body centered at the origin.

To understand how does the differences in the definition of the reference frame effect the obtained result, an experimental spacecraft orbiting around Phobos for [Epoch](#) of 09 Apr 2025 15:00:00.000 has been defined for both BodyFixed and BodyInertial coordinate systems in [NASA GMAT](#). The simulation has been stopped 24000 seconds after [Epoch](#). The spacecraft is orbiting 17 km from the center Phobos with a horizontal velocity of 0.004 km/s.

Figure 4: BodyFixed Reference Frame After 24000 Seconds

Even though same amount of time has passed for both simulations, the orbit around Phobos for the BodyFixed model seems incomplete while the orbit for the BodyInertial model is completed. In reality, both orbits are complete as sufficient time has passed. In BodyFixed reference frame, the coordinate system also rotates with Phobos. This rotation of the coordinate system causes the offset in the visualization

Figure 5: BodyInertial Reference Frame After 24000 Seconds

of the orbit. It must be noted that the different reference frames have different results for vector quantity calculations.

To see the effect of the reference frames on longer missions, the stopping condition of the simulation has been changed to 24000000 seconds after [Epoch](#). To have a more clear view of the difference between two reference frames, the X value, which was previously 17 has been revised as 2000 km.

As the [Fig.6](#) shows, the increase in the distance increased the exposure of the spacecraft to the non-inertial forces. From the first experiment, it has been seen that the Phobos' rotational velocity and the spacecraft's horizontal velocity are not synchronous. As a result, precession is observed in the orbit of the spacecraft ([Fig.6](#)). This simulation shows that the significance of the non-inertial forces increase as the distance from the center object increase.

The [Fig.7](#) shows that the orbit for the BodyInertial reference frame which was circular became elliptical for the second case. This difference is due to the spacecraft's horizontal velocity being too slow to obtain a circular orbit when the distance is increased.

Figure 6: BodyFixed Reference Frame After 24000000 Seconds

Figure 7: BodyInertial Reference Frame After 24000000 Seconds

These experiments enhanced the understanding of the reference frames and their functionalities in [NASA GMAT](#).

3.2.3 Sphere of Influence of Martian Moons'

The **SOI** of Martian moons were calculated. The gravitational parameter of Mars is 4.282837×10^{13} .

The ρ values for the Martian moons are considered and the **SOI** of both moons are calculated.

For **Phobos**, using:

$$k_{\text{Phobos}} = 0.00070934 \times 10^9, \quad \rho = 9376 \times 10^3 \text{ m}$$
$$r_{\text{SOI}} = \left(\frac{0.00070934 \times 10^9}{4.282837 \times 10^{13}} \right)^{\frac{2}{5}} \cdot (9376 \times 10^3) \approx 7238.8 \text{ km}$$

For **Deimos**, using:

$$k_{\text{Deimos}} = 0.000158817 \times 10^9, \quad \rho = 23459 \times 10^3 \text{ m}$$
$$r_{\text{SOI}} = \left(\frac{0.000158817 \times 10^9}{4.282837 \times 10^{13}} \right)^{\frac{2}{5}} \cdot (23459 \times 10^3) \approx 9953.5 \text{ km}$$

These values indicate the radius of the **SOI** from the center of the celestial object. This calculations were used in evaluating whether the gravitational field of the Moon becomes more effective than the gravitational field of Mars.

To indicate the effectiveness of the **SOI** of both moons, the obtained value was compared to the radius of the moon.

For **Phobos**:

$$r_{\text{Phobos}} = 11.267 \text{ km}$$

$$\delta r = 7238.8 - 11267 = -4028.2 \text{ km}$$

For **Deimos**:

$$r_{\text{Deimos}} = 6.2 \text{ km}$$

$$\delta r = 9953.5 - 6.2 = 9947.3 \text{ km}$$

As can be seen from the calculations above, the result of the subtraction for Phobos results in a negative number. This mean the gravitational field of Phobos becomes more effective than the gravitational

field of Mars when spacecraft is closer to the center of Phobos than the surface of Phobos. Obviously, the spacecraft to be lower than the surface of Phobos is not feasible. Therefore, this finding is interpreted as the gravitational field of Phobos never becomes more effective than the gravitational field of Mars. Instead, it causes small perturbations in the trajectory of the spacecraft. As the main objective of this study is to conduct an analysis on the optimizing the accuracy as much as possible and obtaining a realistic trajectory, the effect of the gravitational field of Phobos on the trajectory of the spacecraft is investigated.

3.2.4 NASA GMAT 2025a

On April 18, 2025, a new version of [NASA GMAT](#) has been released. This new version included some important features which further enhanced the study [21]. Some of the new features that effected the current study are the following:

Phobos Ephemeris

With the 2025a release, the [SPICE](#) ephemeris kernel has been updated. This update increases the accuracy of the simulations involving Phobos, as the scientific understanding of the Martian moon advances. The quadratic prime meridian constant of Phobos which were obtained as 8.864000000000000 from 2015 IAU report [17] was replaced with the updated value of 12.72192797000000000000 from the corrections to the mentioned report [18].

Multi-Body Harmonic Propagator

The propagation mechanics in [NASA GMAT](#) is provided by a class called Propagator. Propagator class inherits another class called ForceModel, which is the fundamental for defining key parameters such as the Central Body, Primary Body, Point Masses, [SRP](#), Drag, etc.

Primary Body is the celestial object which the simulation will considers its gravitational field from the provided gravity potential file (.cof). Previous versions of [NASA GMAT](#) allowed only one Primary Body to be inserted. With [NASA GMAT](#) 2025a release, the ForceModel class accepts multiple Primary Bodies and implements their gravitational field simultaneously. [21]

With this improvement, the gravitational fields of Mars and Phobos are implemented concurrently and a more realistic model of the mission is obtained. After making sure that the new [NASA GMAT](#) release is compatible with the previously existing simulation, the mission has been migrated into [NASA GMAT 2025a](#). For the simulation of the flyby to Phobos, the [NASA GMAT 2025a](#) version is used due to its advanced gravitational modelling features in ForceModels.

3.3 Phobos Flyby

One of the main objectives of this mission is to perform a very low altitude flyby to Phobos. To succeed this goal, the mission simulation by Yurttas et al. [19] has been modified to be implemented in the [NASA GMAT 2025a](#). A ForceModel which implements gravitational fields of both Mars and Phobos is defined. The gravitational potential file for Mars, Mars50c.cof, has been obtained from the built-in files of [NASA GMAT](#). To obtain the most realistic simulation, the gravitational field of Phobos and the SPAD file implementation of the spherical "cannonball" method have been implemented.

3.3.1 Gravitational Field of Phobos

The gravitational potential file for Mars was plugged in by [NASA GMAT](#). However, there are no built-in files for Phobos. The gravitational potential file for Phobos was produced as the result of the study by C. Yıldırım [11]. This obtained file have been inserted to [NASA GMAT 2025a](#). The defined ForceModel script can be found in [A.1](#). Different degree and order selections were analyzed and can be found in [Table 3](#). The **Periapsis** is the [RMAG](#) value with respect to Phobos. It must be noted that to see the pure effect of the gravitational field constants of Phobos, the simulation has been sterilized from other implementation which are possibly effective on the flyby distance, such as [SPAD 2025a](#) file implementation. The [NASA GMAT 2025a](#) script for the flyby without the [SPAD](#) file implementation can be found in [A.2](#).

As the [Table 3](#) indicates, the change in the periapsis value becomes less significant for order values higher than 2. The sensitivity of the gravitational field to the higher degree calculations for the same order becomes insignificant after the second term as well. It has been seen that the results converges to a stable

Table 3: Degree and Order Analysis

Degree	Order	Periapsis	Periapsis ElapsedSecs
0	0	30.20437182879114	207400050.1062134
1	0	30.20437182879114	207400050.1062134
1	1	30.20437182879114	207400050.1062134
2	0	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
2	1	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
2	2	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
3	0	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
3	1	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
3	2	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
3	3	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
4	0	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
4	4	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
5	0	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134
5	5	30.20437180201993	207400050.1062134

value for the first degree 5 and order 5 values, therefore the experiment is discontinued.

3.3.2 Spherical Model SPAD File

The experiments by Zengin et al. has shown that inserting an [SPAD](#) file instead of relying on the in-built spherical [SRP](#) model in [NASA GMAT](#) provides a more stable simulation. [10] Therefore, to simulate the [SRP](#) acting on the spacecraft in relatively more reliable way, an [SPAD](#) of the spherical model will be inserted. The [NASA GMAT](#) 2025a script for the flyby with the [SPAD](#) file implementation can be found in [A.3](#). The [Table 4](#) shows the results of the calculation with [SPAD](#) file.

As can be seen from [Table 4](#), the results are much more precise compared to the [Table 3](#). It must be noted that the **Periapsis** values converge by degree 2, unlike the case without the [SPAD](#) file. It can be deducted that with [SPAD](#) file a more realistic and precise measurement can be obtained.

The Phobos flyby simulation is enhanced by the discussed implementations. According to the simulations, the flyby occurs on 04 Dec 2029 05:17:37.720. The minimum flyby distance obtained from these simulation results is 30.20412666711077 kilometers above the center of Phobos, which means nearly 18.9 kilometers above its surface.

Table 4: Degree and Order Analysis With SPAD

Degree	Order	Periapsis	Periapsis ElapsedSecs
0	0	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
1	0	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
1	1	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
2	0	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
2	1	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
2	2	30.20412546274928	207400050.1062115
3	0	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
3	1	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
3	2	30.20412546274928	207400050.1062115
3	3	30.20412546274928	207400050.1062115
4	0	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062115
4	4	30.20412546274928	207400050.1062115
5	0	30.20412549150277	207400050.1062134
5	5	30.20412546274928	207400050.1062115

Figure 8: Phobos Flyby Moment

3.4 Aerobraking

The continuous "Sundiver" maneuvers produce a great amount of [SRP](#) which allows the spacecraft to reach to the Martian system. One of the biggest challenges with the solar sails is decelerating them. As the solar radiation is coming from a certain direction, it is not possible to direct [SRP](#) to the opposite direction of the motion. In order to decelerate, the maneuver known as [Aerobraking](#) is implemented. [Aerobraking](#)

is a maneuver in solar sailing that a celestial object's atmospheric drag is used to decrease the acceleration of the spacecraft by flying close to the celestial object. In this study, the Martian atmosphere is used to perform this maneuver.

3.4.1 Martian Atmosphere

As the atmospheric property of Mars, the exponential atmosphere method has been adopted. This method considers that the effect of the atmospheric drag is increasing exponentially as the spacecraft gets closer to the surface of the celestial object. This is a more realistic approach than the default mechanics of [NASA GMAT](#), which is considering atmosphere as a property is either fully effective or non effective at all.

To implement the atmospheric model in [NASA GMAT](#), the atmospheric model plugin needs to be placed in program folders and *gmat_startup_file.txt* needs to be updated. After the library is ready to use, the related tab of the Propagator that implements the dynamics in the Martian system is clicked. In Drag box, the Exponential model that is required to be implemented has been selected from the drop down menu titled Atmospheric Drag.

3.4.2 Aerobraking Maneuver

After implementing the Martian atmosphere in [NASA GMAT](#), the [Aerobraking](#) maneuver is simulated. After cruising 61 kilometers close to Mars to be influenced by its atmospheric drag, the solar sail changes its attitude to the position which it does not make use of the [SRP](#), letting the spacecraft to be controlled by the Martian atmospheric drag. After [Aerobraking](#), the spacecraft reaches to the apoapsis with respect to the Mars. The final position of the spacecraft is shown in [Fig.9](#). The green line indicates the orbit of Phobos around Mars. The script of the maneuver can be found in [A.4](#).

For spacecraft to enter the orbit of Mars, it must inherit enough energy to climb back up to the Martian orbit after performing a low altitude flyby for [Aerobraking](#). Otherwise, the spacecraft crashes to the Mars' surface. Another constraint for the orbit after [Aerobraking](#) is the mission objective of entering the orbit

Figure 9: Aerobraking in the Martian Atmosphere

around Mars in an altitude close to Phobos to make deeper analysis on the Martian moon. The initial conditions of the spacecraft with respect to the Sun-Ecliptic reference frame which is simulated in Fig. 9 are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Initial Conditions for Aerobraking

Parameter	Value
SMA (km)	101919800.2251111
ECC	0.500000000000001
INC (deg)	2.044399999999658
RAAN (deg)	25.46000000000157
AOP (deg)	89.99500000000239
TA (deg)	99.98914999999776

This conditions result in a **Altitude** value of 5970.78548922857 km with respect to Mars. Considering that Phobos is orbiting Mars with an altitude of 5989 km, this simulation shows that the spacecraft inherits enough energy to climb back in the orbit of Mars, with 19 kilometers distance to Phobos. This result shows that the mission is quantitatively possible.

The acceleration of the spacecraft during the aerobrake is critical. If the acceleration during the

aerobrake exceeds structural limits of the spacecraft's materials, the spacecraft fail mechanically. The **Acceleration** value of the spacecraft has been plotted in Fig.10. It must be noted that the plotted is zoomed to the flyby moment for a better representation, as it is the moment that the acceleration value peaks.

Figure 10: Acceleration of the Spacecraft During Aerobraking

The highest acceleration value during aerobraking is $6.041603547492061 \text{ km/s}^2$. Even though this is quite high for a spacecraft, further improvements on this value is out of the scope of this study. Further notes can be found in Section 5.1.

3.4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

As another objective of the mission focuses on making a realistic trajectory design, sensitivity analysis upon the **Aerobraking** trajectory has been conducted. The first experiment was increasing the semi-major axis **SMA** by 1 meter. As can be seen in Fig.11, the spacecraft flew closer to Mars and could not climb back to orbit, which eventually resulted in the crashing of the spacecraft to Mars.

The second experiment was decreasing the initial **SMA** by 1 meter. As the result of this experiment

Figure 11: Spacecraft Crashed to Mars

which can be seen in Fig.12, the [Aerobraking](#) maneuver was not sufficient enough to keep the spacecraft in the orbit of Mars. Therefore, the spacecraft continued its heliocentric orbit with a small defect in its direction after encountering with the Martian atmosphere for a fraction of a second.

These experiments showed that the trajectory of the aerobraking maneuver of this solar sailing mission is highly sensitive.

Figure 12: Spacecraft Missed Martian Orbit

4 Results and Discussion

This study focused on designing a realistic trajectory for a solar sail-propelled CubeSat. Various improvements were implemented to obtain the most realistic trajectory simulation. Below, some of the key findings of this study are discussed.

4.1 Using NASA GMAT 2025a

The most recent release of [NASA GMAT](#) came out on April 18, 2025. In this release, the ephemerides of Phobos has been updated and a new Multibody Propagator was introduced. The present study centers investigating gravitational field dynamics of Mars and Phobos concurrently. Before Multibody Propagator was introduced, a method which was implemented by previous reseachers was being used. This method required two propagators: one implementing the Mars' gravitational field, and the other implementing Phobos' gravitational field. The propagator was switched according to the distance [RMAG](#) of the space-

craft from the [SOI](#) of Mars. After conducting some case studies to ensure the new release of [NASA GMAT](#) was compatible, the simulation was migrated. With the 2025a release, one Multibody Propagator replaced these two propagators. This improvement provided an in-built dynamic for gravitational field dynamics of Mars and Phobos.

4.2 Gravitational Field of Phobos and Flyby

One of the objectives of the mission plan is performing a low altitude flyby to Phobos. The mission plan from previous years' researches were revised and implemented to [NASA GMAT 2025a](#). The designed trajectory was enhanced by using a very realistic gravitational potential model of Phobos by [11]. The flyby occurred on 04 Dec 2029 05:17:37.720 with a perimeter around 30 kilometers. Considering the radius of Phobos is 11.267 km, the flyby occurs in a nearly 18.7 km distance from the surface of the Moon.

In gravitational potential data, higher degree and order terms are required for more sensitive analysis. Experiments with degree and order values of Phobos' gravitational field has been carried out to see their effect on the flyby distance (See: Table. 3). There was no significant difference for the degrees 0 and 1. The difference in the periapsis result was noticed for the degree 2 for the first time. Calculations for degree 2 and the order 2 gave a precise measurement. For the following experiments, the results obtained from using the degree 2 and order 0 term and the degree 2 and order 2 term were repeated for respective order values for each degree.

It can be said that the spacecraft following this trajectory is sensitive to the gravitational constants of degree 2 and the order 2 at most. A closer flyby might have required higher degree and order terms.

4.3 SRP Modeling by SPAD

The simulation of the trajectory for the Phobos flyby was reproduced by implementing an [SPAD](#) file for the modeling of [SRP](#) which is propagating the solar sail. Even though the [SPAD](#) file used in this experiment was an implementation of spherical, or "cannonball", model that is used as the default model

in [NASA GMAT](#) the results obtained were different from the previous experiment by meters.

From the study by Zengin et al., it is known that the [SPAD](#) file implementation results in a more stable outcome even when spherical is used. [10] Similar observations were made for the Phobos flyby distance. Unlike previous case (See: Table. 3), the periapsis value is improved by including the degree 3 terms (See: Table. 4). Including higher degree and order terms improved the periapsis values. This supports the findings by Zengin et al. on how using [SPAD](#) file stabilizes the trajectory in [NASA GMAT](#) simulations.

4.4 Aerobraking in Martian Atmosphere

Another goal of the study was performing [Aerobraking](#) by using the Martian atmosphere. To implement this simulation, Martian atmosphere was introduced to [NASA GMAT 2025a](#). The Exponential atmosphere model was used for this implementation, as it provides a more realistic approach to the atmospheric dynamics. The initial condition parameters were adjusted accordingly. From the simulations, it has been concluded that it is quantitatively possible to perform an [Aerobraking](#) maneuver with the proposed solar sail and reach the altitude of 5970.8 km in Mars' orbit after [Aerobraking](#). Considering that Phobos is orbiting Mars with the altitude of 5989 km, this simulation also shows that the spacecraft orbiting Mars in the resulting altitude will provide an opportunity for Phobos observations.

An Experimental Case on Mars Orbit

Proposing an orbit for the spacecraft was not in the scope of the study. The parameters of the orbit can be found by future studies. However, a possible direction of the orbit for the spacecraft to enter after aerobraking might look like Fig. 13.

Even though the altitude of the orbit is close, the difference in the planes of the orbit of Phobos and the orbit of the spacecraft should be noticed. It must be noted that a possible study on proposing an orbit for Phobos observations must address this difference.

Figure 13: Spacecraft Missed Martian Orbit

5 Conclusions

This study presented a trajectory design for a solar sail-propelled CubeSat that performs a close flyby of Phobos and uses aerobraking to enter orbit around Mars.

By using enhanced trajectory design tools and a realistic implementation of Phobos' gravitational field, a flyby distance of about 18.9 km from the surface of the Martian moon was achieved. The simulation was enhanced by implementing an [SPAD](#).

A maneuver of [Aerobraking](#) was investigated and marked as quantitatively possible. The [Aerobraking](#) maneuver was investigated for different [SMA](#) values. It has been seen that the trajectory for the [Aerobraking](#) is extremely sensitive.

Overall, this study enhanced the understanding of trajectory design of solar sail-propelled spacecrafts by advancing powerful simulation tools, investigating the effects of gravitational coefficients on trajectory and implementing [Aerobraking](#) maneuver to enter orbit around Mars. The results will be presented alongside with C. Yıldırım and B. Akçit in MetroAerospace'25 by IEEE. [12]

5.1 Future Improvements

The present study aimed to implement a realistic approach to trajectory design of a solar sail-propelled CubeSat. The study also revealed what can be done in future implementations to improve the trajectory design and simulations.

A Realistic SPAD File

A [SPAD](#) file of the proposed spacecraft can be obtained by using advanced CFD simulations or wind tunnel tests. With such file, a more realistic [SRP](#) calculation can be made. With the information on the material of the solar sails, the decay in the solar sails by time can be calculated as well.

Sail Orientation

Current simulations assume the solar sails are either parallel or perpendicular to the Sun. However, the [SRP](#) value is less than the perpendicular situation when the spacecraft is changing the orientation of its sails. This may be simulated by either including a realistic [SPAD](#) file of the spacecraft or defining the [SRP](#) as a function of time in [NASA GMAT](#).

Acceleration During Aerobraking

The acceleration of the spacecraft during [Aerobraking](#) is critical. If the acceleration during [Aerobraking](#) exceeds structural limits of the spacecraft's materials, the spacecraft fails mechanically. To prevent that, the acceleration during aerobraking must carefully studied.

6 Acknowledgements

I would like to sincerely thank Dr. Fabrizio Pinto for his support and guidance throughout every step of this study.

I am also grateful to Darrel Conway from Thinking Systems for his continued assistance, generous support, and encouragement, particularly in connection to our use of the Martian Exponential Atmosphere.

References

- [1] R. A. Battin, *An Introduction To The Mathematics and Methods of Astrodynamics*, 1999.
- [2] G. B. Arfken, *Mathematical Methods for Physicists*, 7th Edition, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2013.
- [3] L. Johnson, J. Castillo-Rogez, B. Cohen, L. McNutt, Solar sail propulsion for interplanetary cubesats, 51st AIAA/SAE/ASEE Joint Propulsion Conference (2015). [doi:10.2514/6.2015-3895](https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2015-3895).
- [4] Y. Guo, D. Feng, X. Wang, C. Li, Y. Liu, The earth-mars transfer trajectory optimization of solar sail based on hp-Adaptive pseudospectral method, *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society* 2018 (2018). [doi:10.1155/2018/6916848](https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/6916848).
- [5] O. Mori, H. Sawada, R. Funase, M. Morimoto, T. Endo, T. Yamamoto, Y. Tsuda, Y. Kawakatsu, J. Kawaguchi, Y. Miyazaki, Y. Shirasawa, D. Team, I. Solar Sail W, First Solar Power Sail Demonstration by IKAROS, *TRANSACTIONS OF THE JAPAN SOCIETY FOR AERONAUTICAL AND SPACE SCIENCES, AEROSPACE TECHNOLOGY JAPAN* 8 (ists27) (2010) To_4_25–To_4_31. [doi:10.2322/tastj.8.To_4_25](https://doi.org/10.2322/tastj.8.To_4_25).
- [6] D. A. Spencer, B. Betts, J. M. Bellardo, A. Diaz, B. Plante, J. R. Mansell, The LightSail 2 solar sailing technology demonstration, *Advances in Space Research* 67 (9) (2021) 2878–2889. [doi:10.1016/j.asr.2020.06.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2020.06.029).
- [7] A. R. Sobey, T. R. Lockett, Design and Development of NEA Scout Solar Sail Deployer Mechanism.
- [8] G. L. Matloff, T. Taylor, C. Powell, T. Moton, PHOBOS / DEIMOS SAMPLE RETURN VIA SOLAR SAIL (Nov. 2004).

- [9] G. L. Matloff, T. Taylor, C. Powell, T. Moton, Phobos/Deimos Sample Return via Solar Sail, *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* Volume 1065 (Issue 1: New Trends in Astrodynamics and Applications) 429–440. [doi:10.1196/annals.1370.013](https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1370.013).
- [10] C. Zengin, C. Oral, İ. E. Özer, T. Turhan, Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting Mars and its moons (Jul. 2023). [doi:10.5281/ZENODO.8191968](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8191968).
- [11] C. Yildirim, Analysis of the effects of uncertainties in the gravitational field of Phobos on the execution of very low altitude flybys by a solar sail-propelled SmallSat orbiting Mars. Zenodo: To appear(2025).
- [12] B. Akcıt, O. Ozturk, C. Yildirim, A solar sail-propelled SmallSat mission to Phobos: Gravitational field uncertainties, trajectory design, and situational awareness IEEE MetroAerospace 2025 To appear(2025).
- [13] E. Joffre, M. Zamaro, N. Silva, A. Marcos, P. Simplício, Trajectory design and guidance for landing on Phobos, *Acta Astronautica* 151 (2018) 389–400. [doi:10.1016/j.actaastro.2018.06.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2018.06.024).
- [14] A. J. Tang, X. Wu, An interplanetary mission design of a solar sailing CubeSat to mars, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 1509 (1) (2020) 012026. [doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1509/1/012026](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1509/1/012026).
- [15] T. Percy, T. Taylor, T. Powell, A study of possible solar sail applications for mars missions (2004) 1–7 [doi:10.2514/6.2004-3996](https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2004-3996).
- [16] SP. Hughes, NASA GMAT Documentation (2007).
- [17] B. A. Archinal, C. H. Acton, M. F. A’Hearn, A. Conrad, G. J. Consolmagno, T. Duxbury, D. Hestroffer, J. L. Hilton, R. L. Kirk, S. A. Klioner, D. McCarthy, K. Meech, J. Oberst, J. Ping, P. K.

- Seidelmann, D. J. Tholen, P. C. Thomas, I. P. Williams, Report of the IAU Working Group on Cartographic Coordinates and Rotational Elements: 2015, *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy* 130 (3) (2018) 22. [doi:10.1007/s10569-017-9805-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10569-017-9805-5).
- [18] B. A. Archinal, C. H. Acton, A. Conrad, T. Duxbury, D. Hestroffer, J. L. Hilton, L. Jorda, R. L. Kirk, S. A. Klioner, J.-L. Margot, K. Meech, J. Oberst, F. Paganelli, J. Ping, P. K. Seidelmann, A. Stark, D. J. Tholen, Y. Wang, I. P. Williams, Correction to: Report of the IAU Working Group on Cartographic Coordinates and Rotational Elements: 2015, *Celestial Mechanics and Dynamical Astronomy* 131 (12) (2019) 61. [doi:10.1007/s10569-019-9925-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10569-019-9925-1).
- [19] M. Yurttas, B. Atakan, S. S. Mumcuoğlu, Trajectory design and flight dynamics of a realistic solar-sail propelled CubeSat class spacecraft targeting orbits around Mars and its moons (Jun. 2024). [doi:10.5281/ZENODO.11651856](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11651856).
- [20] NASA NAIF Planetary Data System, https://naif.jpl.nasa.gov/pub/naif/generic_kernels/spk/satellites/a/_old/_versions/.
- [21] GMAT 2025a Release Notes, <https://gmt.atlassian.net/projects/GMT/versions/11503/tab/release-report-all-issues>.

A Appendix

A.1 Multibody ForceModel Definition in NASA GMAT 2025a for Phobos Flyby

```
Create ForceModel FM;
FM.CentralBody = Mars;
FM.PrimaryBodies = {Mars, Phobos};
FM.PointMasses = {Sun};
FM.SRP = On;
FM.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
FM.ErrorControl = None;
FM.GravityField.Mars.Degree = 50;
FM.GravityField.Mars.Order = 50;
FM.GravityField.Mars.StmLimit = 100;
FM.GravityField.Mars.PotentialFile = 'C:\Program Files\GMAT-2025a\data\
    gravity\mars\Mars50c.cof';
FM.GravityField.Mars.TideModel = 'None';
FM.GravityField.Phobos.Degree = 5;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.Order = 5;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.StmLimit = 100;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.PotentialFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\
    Phobos-Willner-4x4-coeff-500.0.cof';
FM.SRP.Flux = 1367;
FM.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;
FM.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;
FM.Drag.AtmosphereModel = TSExponentialAtmosphere;
FM.Drag.F107 = 150;
FM.Drag.F107A = 150;
FM.Drag.MagneticIndex = 3;
FM.Drag.DragModel = 'Spherical';
```

A.2 NASA GMAT 2025a Phobos Flyby Script

```
% Multibody spherical harmonic gravity
%-----
%----- User-Defined Celestial Bodies
%-----

Create Moon Phobos;
Phobos.NAIFId = 401;
Phobos.OrbitSpiceKernelName = {'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\mar085.
    bsp'};
```

```

Phobos.OrbitColor = [153 217 134];
Phobos.TargetColor = [154 213 125];
Phobos.EquatorialRadius = 13.5;
Phobos.Flattening = 0.3185185185185186;
Phobos.Mu = 0.00070934;
Phobos.PosVelSource = 'SPICE';
Phobos.CentralBody = 'Mars';
Phobos.RotationDataSource = 'IAUSimplified';
Phobos.OrientationEpoch = 21545;
Phobos.SpinAxisRAConstant = 0;
Phobos.SpinAxisRARate = -0.641;
Phobos.SpinAxisDECConstant = 90;
Phobos.SpinAxisDECRate = -0.5570000000000001;
Phobos.RotationConstant = 190.147;
Phobos.RotationRate = 360.9856235;
Phobos.TextureMapFileName = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Maps\
    combined_phobos_lon_zero_center_small720x360.jpg';
Phobos.3DModelFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\Phobos_1_1000-2WFE
    .3ds';
Phobos.3DModelOffsetX = 0;
Phobos.3DModelOffsetY = 0;
Phobos.3DModelOffsetZ = 0;
Phobos.3DModelRotationX = 90;
Phobos.3DModelRotationY = 0;
Phobos.3DModelRotationZ = 0;
Phobos.3DModelScale = 1;

Create Moon Deimos;
Deimos.NAIFId = 402;
Deimos.OrbitSpiceKernelName = {'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\mar085.
    bsp'};
Deimos.OrbitColor = Tan;
Deimos.TargetColor = DarkGray;
Deimos.EquatorialRadius = 7.5;
Deimos.Flattening = 0.30666666666666666;
Deimos.Mu = 0.000158817;
Deimos.PosVelSource = 'SPICE';
Deimos.CentralBody = 'Mars';
Deimos.RotationDataSource = 'IAUSimplified';
Deimos.OrientationEpoch = 21545;
Deimos.SpinAxisRAConstant = 0;
Deimos.SpinAxisRARate = -0.641;
Deimos.SpinAxisDECConstant = 90;

```

```

Deimos.SpinAxisDECRate = -0.5570000000000001;
Deimos.RotationConstant = 190.147;
Deimos.RotationRate = 360.9856235;
Deimos.TextureMapFileName = 'C:\Program Files\GMAT\data\graphics\texture\
    GenericCelestialBody.jpg';
Deimos.3DModelFile = '';
Deimos.3DModelOffsetX = 0;
Deimos.3DModelOffsetY = 0;
Deimos.3DModelOffsetZ = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationX = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationY = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationZ = 0;
Deimos.3DModelScale = 10;

%-----
%----- Spacecraft
%-----

Create Spacecraft MarsSolarSailSC;

MarsSolarSailSC.DateFormat = UTCGregorian;
MarsSolarSailSC.Epoch = '09 May 2023 18:10:07.614';
MarsSolarSailSC.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
MarsSolarSailSC.DisplayStateType = Keplerian;
MarsSolarSailSC.SMA = 101920000.0000042;
MarsSolarSailSC.ECC = 0.5000000000000001;
MarsSolarSailSC.INC = 2.044420050000277;
MarsSolarSailSC.RAAN = 25.460097499999958;
MarsSolarSailSC.AOP = 89.99499900000099;
MarsSolarSailSC.TA = 99.98909999999991;
MarsSolarSailSC.DryMass = 40;
MarsSolarSailSC.Cd = 2.2;
MarsSolarSailSC.Cr = 0.8;
MarsSolarSailSC.DragArea = 900;
MarsSolarSailSC.SRPArea = 900;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADDragScaleFactor = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADSRPScaleFactor = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.AtmosDensityScaleFactor = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.ExtendedMassPropertiesModel = 'None';
MarsSolarSailSC.NAIFId = -10001001;
MarsSolarSailSC.NAIFIdReferenceFrame = -9001001;
MarsSolarSailSC.OrbitColor = Red;
MarsSolarSailSC.TargetColor = Teal;

```

```

MarsSolarSailSC.OrbitErrorCovariance = [ 1e+70 0 0 0 0 0 ; 0 1e+70 0 0 0 0 ;
      0 0 1e+70 0 0 0 ; 0 0 0 1e+70 0 0 ; 0 0 0 0 1e+70 0 ; 0 0 0 0 0 1e+70 ];
MarsSolarSailSC.CdSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.CrSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.Id = 'SatId';
MarsSolarSailSC.Attitude = CoordinateSystemFixed;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADSRPInterpolationMethod = Bilinear;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADSRPScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADDragInterpolationMethod = Bilinear;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADDragScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.AtmosDensityScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\SolarSail-
      concept2.3ds';
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelOffsetX = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelOffsetY = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelOffsetZ = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelRotationX = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelRotationY = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelRotationZ = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelScale = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.AttitudeDisplayStateType = 'Quaternion';
MarsSolarSailSC.AttitudeRateDisplayStateType = 'AngularVelocity';
MarsSolarSailSC.AttitudeCoordinateSystem = EarthMJ2000Eq;
MarsSolarSailSC.EulerAngleSequence = '321';

%-----
%----- ForceModels
%-----

Create ForceModel FM;
FM.CentralBody = Mars;
FM.PrimaryBodies = {Mars, Phobos};
FM.PointMasses = {Sun};
FM.SRP = On;
FM.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
FM.ErrorControl = None;
FM.GravityField.Mars.Degree = 50;
FM.GravityField.Mars.Order = 50;
FM.GravityField.Mars.StmLimit = 100;
FM.GravityField.Mars.PotentialFile = 'C:\Program Files\GMAT-2025a\data\
      gravity\mars\Mars50c.cof';
FM.GravityField.Mars.TideModel = 'None';
FM.GravityField.Phobos.Degree = 5;

```

```

FM.GravityField.Phobos.Order = 5;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.StmLimit = 100;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.PotentialFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\
    Phobos-Willner-4x4-coeff-500.0.cof';
FM.SRP.Flux = 1367;
FM.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;
FM.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;
FM.Drag.AtmosphereModel = TSExponentialAtmosphere;
FM.Drag.F107 = 150;
FM.Drag.F107A = 150;
FM.Drag.MagneticIndex = 3;
FM.Drag.DragModel = 'Spherical';

Create ForceModel ToApo_ForceModel;
ToApo_ForceModel.CentralBody = Sun;
ToApo_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune, Pluto
    , Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
ToApo_ForceModel.Drag = None;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP = On;
ToApo_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
ToApo_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.Flux = 1367;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;

Create ForceModel ToPeri_ForceModel;
ToPeri_ForceModel.CentralBody = Sun;
ToPeri_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune,
    Pluto, Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
ToPeri_ForceModel.Drag = None;
ToPeri_ForceModel.SRP = Off;
ToPeri_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
ToPeri_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;

%-----
%----- Propagators
%-----

Create Propagator Prop;
Prop.FM = FM;

Prop.Type = RungeKutta89;
Prop.InitialStepSize = 60;

```

```

Prop.Accuracy = 1e-15;
Prop.MinStep = 1e-05;
Prop.MaxStep = 2700;
Prop.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
Prop.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator ToApo;
ToApo.FM = ToApo_ForceModel;
ToApo.Type = RungeKutta89;
ToApo.InitialStepSize = 60;
ToApo.Accuracy = 1e-14;
ToApo.MinStep = 21600;
ToApo.MaxStep = 21600;
ToApo.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
ToApo.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator ToPeri;
ToPeri.FM = ToPeri_ForceModel;
ToPeri.Type = RungeKutta89;
ToPeri.InitialStepSize = 60;
ToPeri.Accuracy = 1e-14;
ToPeri.MinStep = 21600;
ToPeri.MaxStep = 21600;
ToPeri.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
ToPeri.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

%-----
%----- Coordinate Systems
%-----

Create CoordinateSystem MarsMJ2000Eq;

MarsMJ2000Eq.Origin = Mars;
MarsMJ2000Eq.Axes = MJ2000Eq;

%
%   Set up visualizations
%

Create CoordinateSystem EML2;
EML2.Origin = Mars;
EML2.Axes = ObjectReferenced;
EML2.XAxis = R;

```

```

EML2.ZAxis = N;
EML2.Primary = Mars;
EML2.Secondary = Phobos;

Create CoordinateSystem SunEcliptic;
SunEcliptic.Origin = Sun;
SunEcliptic.Axes = MJ2000Ec;

Create CoordinateSystem MarsSolarSailSCRef;
MarsSolarSailSCRef.Origin = MarsSolarSailSC;
MarsSolarSailSCRef.Axes = MJ2000Ec;

Create CoordinateSystem PhobosCentered;
PhobosCentered.Origin = Phobos;
PhobosCentered.Axes = MJ2000Eq;

%-----
%----- Subscribers
%-----

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames1;
OpenFrames1.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames1.UpperLeft = [ 0.04176470588235294 0.1202127659574468 ];
OpenFrames1.Size = [ 0.8441176470588235 0.6893617021276596 ];
OpenFrames1.RelativeZOrder = 68;
OpenFrames1.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames1.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Sun, Mars, Deimos, Phobos};
OpenFrames1.View = {NewView1};
OpenFrames1.CoordinateSystem = MarsSolarSailSCRef;
OpenFrames1.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawAxes = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawLabel = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawGrid = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames1.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames1.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames1.Axes = On;

```

```

OpenFrames1.AxesLength = 1;
OpenFrames1.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames1.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames1.XYPlane = Off;
OpenFrames1.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames1.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames1.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames1.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames1.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames1.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames1.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames1.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames1.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames1.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames1.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames1.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames1.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames1.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames1.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames1.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames1.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right', 'Top-Right'};

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames2;
OpenFrames2.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames2.UpperLeft = [ 0.1052941176470588 0.3638297872340426 ];
OpenFrames2.Size = [ 0.85 0.4095744680851064 ];
OpenFrames2.RelativeZOrder = 27;
OpenFrames2.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames2.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Deimos, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OpenFrames2.View = {ToPhobos, ToDeimos};
OpenFrames2.CoordinateSystem = MarsSolarSailSCRef;
OpenFrames2.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawAxes = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawLabel = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawCenterPoint = [ true false false false true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawEndPoints = [ true false false false true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawGrid = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 1000 ];

```

```

OpenFrames2.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 20 ];
OpenFrames2.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 5 ];
OpenFrames2.Axes = Off;
OpenFrames2.AxesLength = 1;
OpenFrames2.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames2.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames2.XYPlane = Off;
OpenFrames2.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames2.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames2.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames2.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames2.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames2.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames2.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames2.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames2.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames2.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames2.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames2.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames2.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames2.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames2.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames2.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames2.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right', 'Top-Right'};

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames3;
OpenFrames3.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames3.UpperLeft = [ 2.206470588235294 0.2329787234042553 ];
OpenFrames3.Size = [ 1.137647058823529 0.6531914893617021 ];
OpenFrames3.RelativeZOrder = 19;
OpenFrames3.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames3.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Mars, Phobos};
OpenFrames3.View = {CoordinateSystemView1};
OpenFrames3.CoordinateSystem = MarsMJ2000Eq;
OpenFrames3.DrawObject = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawAxes = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawLabel = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawEndpoints = [ true true true ];

```

```

OpenFrames3.DrawVelocity = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawGrid = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames3.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames3.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames3.Axes = On;
OpenFrames3.AxesLength = 12756.2726;
OpenFrames3.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames3.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames3.XYPlane = On;
OpenFrames3.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames3.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames3.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames3.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames3.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames3.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames3.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames3.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames3.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames3.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames3.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames3.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames3.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames3.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames3.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames3.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames3.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right'};

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames4;
OpenFrames4.SolverIterations = Current;

OpenFrames4.UpperLeft = [ 1.092352941176471 0 ];
OpenFrames4.Size = [ 1.092352941176471 1.006382978723404 ];
OpenFrames4.RelativeZOrder = 11;
OpenFrames4.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames4.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OpenFrames4.View = {NewView1};
OpenFrames4.CoordinateSystem = EML2;
OpenFrames4.DrawObject = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawAxes = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawLabel = [ true true true true ];

```

```

OpenFrames4.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawGrid = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames4.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames4.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames4.Axes = On;
OpenFrames4.AxesLength = 12756.2726;
OpenFrames4.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames4.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames4.XYPlane = On;
OpenFrames4.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames4.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames4.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames4.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames4.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames4.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames4.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames4.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames4.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames4.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames4.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames4.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames4.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames4.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames4.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames4.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames4.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right'};

Create ReportFile ReportFile1;
ReportFile1.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile1.UpperLeft = [ -19.37058823529412 0.1627659574468085 ];
ReportFile1.Size = [ 1.138823529411765 0.9712765957446808 ];
ReportFile1.RelativeZOrder = 77;
ReportFile1.Maximized = false;
ReportFile1.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3.txt';
ReportFile1.Precision = 16;
ReportFile1.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.UTCGregorian, MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs,
    MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.

```

```

    Phobos.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.Deimos.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.
    ToApo_ForceModel.Acceleration, MarsSolarSailSC.ToPeri_ForceModel.
    Acceleration, MarsSolarSailSC.FM.Acceleration, MarsSolarSailSC.
    PhobosCentered.VMAG});
ReportFile1.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile1.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile1.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile1.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile1.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile1.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile1.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile1.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create OrbitView OrbitView1;
OrbitView1.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView1.UpperLeft = [ 1.235882352941176 0 ];
OrbitView1.Size = [ 0.8852941176470588 0.8723404255319149 ];
OrbitView1.RelativeZOrder = 24;
OrbitView1.Maximized = false;
OrbitView1.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Deimos, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OrbitView1.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView1.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OrbitView1.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
OrbitView1.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView1.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView1.ShowPlot = true;
OrbitView1.MaxPlotPoints = 200000;
OrbitView1.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView1.ViewPointReference = SolarSystemBarycenter;
OrbitView1.ViewPointVector = [ 0 0 12000000000 ];
OrbitView1.ViewDirection = Sun;
OrbitView1.ViewScaleFactor = 0.05;
OrbitView1.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView1.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView1.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView1.XYPlane = Off;
OrbitView1.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView1.Axes = On;
OrbitView1.Grid = Off;
OrbitView1.SunLine = Off;
OrbitView1.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView1.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView1.EnableStars = On;

```

```

OrbitView1.EnableConstellations = Off;

Create XYPlot XYPlot1;
XYPlot1.SolverIterations = Current;
XYPlot1.UpperLeft = [ 1.078235294117647 0.7170212765957447 ];
XYPlot1.Size = [ 0.5035294117647059 0.4712765957446808 ];
XYPlot1.RelativeZOrder = 16;
XYPlot1.Maximized = false;
XYPlot1.XVariable = MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs;
XYPlot1.YVariables = {MarsSolarSailSC.Phobos.RMAG};
XYPlot1.ShowGrid = true;
XYPlot1.ShowPlot = true;

Create ReportFile coordinates;
coordinates.SolverIterations = Current;
coordinates.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
coordinates.Size = [ 0 0 ];
coordinates.RelativeZOrder = 0;
coordinates.Maximized = false;
coordinates.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-coordinates.txt';
coordinates.Precision = 16;
coordinates.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.A1ModJulian, MarsSolarSailSC.SunEcliptic.X
    , MarsSolarSailSC.SunEcliptic.Y, MarsSolarSailSC.SunEcliptic.Z};
coordinates.WriteHeader = true;
coordinates.LeftJustify = On;
coordinates.ZeroFill = Off;
coordinates.FixedWidth = true;
coordinates.Delimiter = ' ';
coordinates.ColumnWidth = 23;
coordinates.WriteReport = true;
coordinates.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile2;
ReportFile2.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile2.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile2.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile2.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile2.Maximized = false;
ReportFile2.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-earth.txt';
ReportFile2.Precision = 16;
ReportFile2.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.A1ModJulian, Earth.SunEcliptic.X, Earth.

```

```

    SunEcliptic.Y, Earth.SunEcliptic.Z});
ReportFile2.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile2.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile2.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile2.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile2.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile2.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile2.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile2.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile3;
ReportFile3.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile3.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile3.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile3.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile3.Maximized = false;
ReportFile3.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-mars.txt';
ReportFile3.Precision = 16;
ReportFile3.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.A1ModJulian, Mars.SunEcliptic.X, Mars.
    SunEcliptic.Y, Mars.SunEcliptic.Z});
ReportFile3.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile3.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile3.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile3.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile3.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile3.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile3.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile3.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile4;
ReportFile4.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile4.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile4.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile4.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile4.Maximized = false;
ReportFile4.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-phobos.txt';
ReportFile4.Precision = 16;
ReportFile4.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.A1ModJulian, Phobos.SunEcliptic.X, Phobos.
    SunEcliptic.Y, Phobos.SunEcliptic.Z});
ReportFile4.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile4.LeftJustify = On;

```

```

ReportFile4.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile4.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile4.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile4.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile4.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile4.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile5;
ReportFile5.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile5.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile5.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile5.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile5.Maximized = false;
ReportFile5.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-deimos.txt';
ReportFile5.Precision = 16;
ReportFile5.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.A1ModJulian, Deimos.SunEcliptic.X, Deimos.
    SunEcliptic.Y, Deimos.SunEcliptic.Z};
ReportFile5.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile5.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile5.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile5.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile5.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile5.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile5.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile5.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create OrbitView OrbitView2;
OrbitView2.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView2.UpperLeft = [ 0.2964705882352941 0.06170212765957447 ];
OrbitView2.Size = [ 0.4994117647058823 0.4095744680851064 ];
OrbitView2.RelativeZOrder = 39;
OrbitView2.Maximized = false;
OrbitView2.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Mars, Phobos};
OrbitView2.CoordinateSystem = PhobosCentered;
OrbitView2.DrawObject = [ true true true ];
OrbitView2.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
OrbitView2.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView2.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView2.ShowPlot = true;
OrbitView2.MaxPlotPoints = 20000;
OrbitView2.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView2.ViewPointReference = Phobos;

```

```

OrbitView2.ViewPointVector = Phobos;
OrbitView2.ViewDirection = Phobos;
OrbitView2.ViewScaleFactor = 1;
OrbitView2.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = PhobosCentered;
OrbitView2.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView2.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView2.XYPlane = On;
OrbitView2.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView2.Axes = On;
OrbitView2.Grid = Off;
OrbitView2.SunLine = Off;
OrbitView2.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView2.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView2.EnableStars = On;
OrbitView2.EnableConstellations = On;

Create OrbitView OrbitView3;
OrbitView3.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView3.UpperLeft = [ 0.03470588235294118 0.4712765957446808 ];
OrbitView3.Size = [ 0.5 0.4446808510638298 ];
OrbitView3.RelativeZOrder = 43;
OrbitView3.Maximized = false;
OrbitView3.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Deimos, Mars, Phobos, Sun, Earth};
OrbitView3.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView3.DrawObject = [ true true true true true true ];
OrbitView3.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
OrbitView3.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView3.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView3.ShowPlot = true;
OrbitView3.MaxPlotPoints = 20000;
OrbitView3.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView3.ViewPointReference = SolarSystemBarycenter;
OrbitView3.ViewPointVector = [ 0 0 12000000000 ];
OrbitView3.ViewDirection = Sun;
OrbitView3.ViewScaleFactor = 0.05;
OrbitView3.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView3.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView3.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView3.XYPlane = Off;
OrbitView3.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView3.Axes = On;
OrbitView3.Grid = Off;
OrbitView3.SunLine = Off;

```

```

OrbitView3.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView3.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView3.EnableStars = On;
OrbitView3.EnableConstellations = Off;

%-----
%----- Arrays, Variables, Strings
%-----

Create Variable I;

%-----
%----- User Objects
%-----

Create OpenFramesView NewView1;
NewView1.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
NewView1.ViewTrajectory = Off;
NewView1.InertialFrame = On;
NewView1.LookAtFrame = Mars;
NewView1.ShortestAngle = On;
NewView1.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
NewView1.SetCurrentLocation = On;
NewView1.CurrentEye = [ -73.003693995368 2.931034220554193 74.29544063420002
];
NewView1.CurrentCenter = [ -0.4300541023694535 -0.435680262375175
-0.8950808158551808 ];
NewView1.CurrentUp = [ -0.3337969162761715 0.8707114396414417
-0.3611664540929106 ];
NewView1.FOVy = 45;

%-----
%----- User Objects
%-----

Create OpenFramesView CoordinateSystemView1;

CoordinateSystemView1.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
CoordinateSystemView1.ViewTrajectory = Off;
CoordinateSystemView1.InertialFrame = On;
CoordinateSystemView1.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
CoordinateSystemView1.SetCurrentLocation = On;
CoordinateSystemView1.CurrentEye = [ 1850041031.404626 -1004383761.62577
2547773627.111391 ];

```

```

CoordinateSystemView1.CurrentCenter = [ -0.4300539493560791
    -0.435680627822876 -0.89508056640625 ];
CoordinateSystemView1.CurrentUp = [ -0.7253426376049033 0.2701076349345477
    0.6331823778520901 ];
CoordinateSystemView1.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView ToPhobos;
ToPhobos.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
ToPhobos.ViewTrajectory = On;
ToPhobos.InertialFrame = Off;
ToPhobos.LookAtFrame = Phobos;
ToPhobos.ShortestAngle = Off;
ToPhobos.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
ToPhobos.SetCurrentLocation = On;
ToPhobos.CurrentEye = [ 9.907448257284202 55.98915006526367 69.55493618895487
    ];
ToPhobos.CurrentCenter = [ 0 7.105427357601002e-15 0 ];
ToPhobos.CurrentUp = [ 0.8988987279915501 0.2698119402408852
    -0.3452283211421425 ];
ToPhobos.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView ToDeimos;
ToDeimos.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
ToDeimos.ViewTrajectory = On;
ToDeimos.InertialFrame = Off;
ToDeimos.LookAtFrame = Deimos;
ToDeimos.ShortestAngle = Off;
ToDeimos.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
ToDeimos.SetCurrentLocation = On;
ToDeimos.CurrentEye = [ 0 -10.40346197926335 0 ];
ToDeimos.CurrentCenter = [ 0 0 0 ];
ToDeimos.CurrentUp = [ 0 0 1 ];
ToDeimos.FOVy = 45;

%-----
%----- Mission Sequence
%-----

BeginMissionSequence;
Propagate 'ToPeri' ToPeri(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.Periapsis,
    OrbitColor = [255 128 64]};
For I = 1:1:6;
    Propagate 'ToApo' ToApo(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.Apoapsis,

```

```

        OrbitColor = [0 255 0]);
    Propagate 'ToPeri' ToPeri(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.Periapsis,
        OrbitColor = [255 0 0]};
EndFor;
Propagate 'Mars' ToApo(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.RMAG = 578000,
    OrbitColor = [255 0 128]};
Propagate 'Multibody' Prop(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Phobos.Periapsis
    , StopTolerance = 1e-10, OrbitColor = [255 128 255]};
Stop;

```

A.3 NASA GMAT 2025a Phobos Flyby Script With SPAD

```

% Multibody spherical harmonic gravity
%-----
%----- User-Defined Celestial Bodies
%-----

Create Moon Phobos;
Phobos.NAIFId = 401;
Phobos.OrbitSpiceKernelName = {'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\mar085.
    bsp'};
Phobos.OrbitColor = [153 217 134];
Phobos.TargetColor = [154 213 125];
Phobos.EquatorialRadius = 13.5;
Phobos.Flattening = 0.3185185185185186;
Phobos.Mu = 0.00070934;
Phobos.PosVelSource = 'SPICE';
Phobos.CentralBody = 'Mars';
Phobos.RotationDataSource = 'IAUSimplified';
Phobos.OrientationEpoch = 21545;
Phobos.SpinAxisRAConstant = 0;
Phobos.SpinAxisRARate = -0.641;
Phobos.SpinAxisDECConstant = 90;
Phobos.SpinAxisDECRate = -0.5570000000000001;
Phobos.RotationConstant = 190.147;
Phobos.RotationRate = 360.9856235;
Phobos.TextureMapFileName = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Maps\
    combined_phobos_lon_zero_center_small1720x360.jpg';
Phobos.3DModelFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\phobos-willner14-
    used-for-calculation.3ds';
Phobos.3DModelOffsetX = 0;
Phobos.3DModelOffsetY = 0;

```

```

Phobos.3DModelOffsetZ = 0;
Phobos.3DModelRotationX = 90;
Phobos.3DModelRotationY = 0;
Phobos.3DModelRotationZ = 0;
Phobos.3DModelScale = 1;

Create Moon Deimos;
Deimos.NAIFId = 402;
Deimos.OrbitSpiceKernelName = {'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\mar085.
    bsp'};
Deimos.OrbitColor = Tan;
Deimos.TargetColor = DarkGray;
Deimos.EquatorialRadius = 7.5;
Deimos.Flattening = 0.30666666666666666;
Deimos.Mu = 0.000158817;
Deimos.PosVelSource = 'SPICE';
Deimos.CentralBody = 'Mars';
Deimos.RotationDataSource = 'IAUSimplified';
Deimos.OrientationEpoch = 21545;
Deimos.SpinAxisRAConstant = 0;
Deimos.SpinAxisRARate = -0.641;
Deimos.SpinAxisDECConstant = 90;
Deimos.SpinAxisDECRate = -0.5570000000000001;
Deimos.RotationConstant = 190.147;
Deimos.RotationRate = 360.9856235;
Deimos.TextureMapFileName = 'C:\Program Files\GMAT\data\graphics\texture\
    GenericCelestialBody.jpg';
Deimos.3DModelFile = '';
Deimos.3DModelOffsetX = 0;
Deimos.3DModelOffsetY = 0;
Deimos.3DModelOffsetZ = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationX = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationY = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationZ = 0;
Deimos.3DModelScale = 10;

%-----
%----- Spacecraft
%-----

Create Spacecraft PropSat;

PropSat.DateFormat = UTCGregorian;

```

```

PropSat.Epoch = '09 May 2023 18:10:07.614';
PropSat.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
PropSat.DisplayStateType = Keplerian;
PropSat.SMA = 101920000.0000045;
PropSat.ECC = 0.5000000000000006;
PropSat.INC = 2.044420050000277;
PropSat.RAAN = 25.46009749999973;
PropSat.AOP = 89.99499900000096;
PropSat.TA = 99.98909999999886;
PropSat.DryMass = 40;
PropSat.Cd = 2.2;
PropSat.Cr = 0.8;
PropSat.DragArea = 900;
PropSat.SRPArea = 900;
PropSat.SPADDragScaleFactor = 1;
PropSat.SPADSRPScaleFactor = 1;
PropSat.AtmosDensityScaleFactor = 1;
PropSat.ExtendedMassPropertiesModel = 'None';
PropSat.NAIFId = -10001001;
PropSat.NAIFIdReferenceFrame = -9001001;
PropSat.OrbitColor = Red;
PropSat.TargetColor = Teal;
PropSat.OrbitErrorCovariance = [ 1e+70 0 0 0 0 0 ; 0 1e+70 0 0 0 0 ; 0 0 1e
    +70 0 0 0 ; 0 0 0 1e+70 0 0 ; 0 0 0 0 1e+70 0 ; 0 0 0 0 0 1e+70 ];
PropSat.CdSigma = 1e+70;
PropSat.CrSigma = 1e+70;
PropSat.Id = 'SatId';
PropSat.Attitude = CoordinateSystemFixed;
PropSat.SPADSRPFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\SPADFiles\testout-with
    -header-1.spo';
PropSat.SPADSRPInterpolationMethod = Bilinear;
PropSat.SPADSRPScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
PropSat.SPADDragInterpolationMethod = Bilinear;
PropSat.SPADDragScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
PropSat.AtmosDensityScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
PropSat.ModelFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\SolarSail-concept2
    .3ds';
PropSat.ModelOffsetX = 0;
PropSat.ModelOffsetY = 0;
PropSat.ModelOffsetZ = 0;
PropSat.ModelRotationX = 0;
PropSat.ModelRotationY = 0;
PropSat.ModelRotationZ = 0;

```

```

PropSat.ModelScale = 0.001;
PropSat.AttitudeDisplayStateType = 'Quaternion';
PropSat.AttitudeRateDisplayStateType = 'AngularVelocity';
PropSat.AttitudeCoordinateSystem = EarthMJ2000Eq;
PropSat.EulerAngleSequence = '321';

%-----
%----- ForceModels
%-----

Create ForceModel FM;
FM.CentralBody = Mars;
FM.PrimaryBodies = {Phobos, Mars};
FM.PointMasses = {Sun};
FM.Drag = None;
FM.SRP = On;
FM.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
FM.ErrorControl = None;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.Degree = 2;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.Order = 2;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.StmLimit = 100;
FM.GravityField.Phobos.PotentialFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\
    Phobos-Willner-4x4-coeff-500.0.cof';
FM.GravityField.Mars.Degree = 50;
FM.GravityField.Mars.Order = 50;
FM.GravityField.Mars.StmLimit = 100;
FM.GravityField.Mars.PotentialFile = 'C:\Program Files\GMAT-2025a\data\
    gravity\mars\Mars50c.cof';
FM.GravityField.Mars.TideModel = 'None';
FM.SRP.Flux = 1367;
FM.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;
FM.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;

Create ForceModel ToApo_ForceModel;
ToApo_ForceModel.CentralBody = Sun;
ToApo_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune, Pluto
    , Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
ToApo_ForceModel.Drag = None;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP = On;
ToApo_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
ToApo_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.Flux = 1367;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;

```

```

ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;

Create ForceModel ToPeri_ForceModel;
ToPeri_ForceModel.CentralBody = Sun;
ToPeri_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune,
    Pluto, Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
ToPeri_ForceModel.Drag = None;
ToPeri_ForceModel.SRP = Off;
ToPeri_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
ToPeri_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;

%-----
%----- Propagators
%-----

Create Propagator Prop;
Prop.FM = FM;

Prop.Type = RungeKutta89;
Prop.InitialStepSize = 60;
Prop.Accuracy = 1e-15;
Prop.MinStep = 1e-05;
Prop.MaxStep = 2700;
Prop.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
Prop.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator ToApo;
ToApo.FM = ToApo_ForceModel;
ToApo.Type = RungeKutta89;
ToApo.InitialStepSize = 60;
ToApo.Accuracy = 1e-14;
ToApo.MinStep = 21600;
ToApo.MaxStep = 21600;
ToApo.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
ToApo.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator ToPeri;
ToPeri.FM = ToPeri_ForceModel;
ToPeri.Type = RungeKutta89;
ToPeri.InitialStepSize = 60;
ToPeri.Accuracy = 1e-14;
ToPeri.MinStep = 21600;
ToPeri.MaxStep = 21600;

```

```

ToPeri.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
ToPeri.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

%-----
%----- Coordinate Systems
%-----

Create CoordinateSystem MarsMJ2000Eq;

MarsMJ2000Eq.Origin = Mars;
MarsMJ2000Eq.Axes = MJ2000Eq;

%
%   Set up visualizations
%

Create CoordinateSystem EML2;
EML2.Origin = Mars;
EML2.Axes = ObjectReferenced;
EML2.XAxis = R;
EML2.ZAxis = N;
EML2.Primary = Mars;
EML2.Secondary = Phobos;

Create CoordinateSystem SunEcliptic;
SunEcliptic.Origin = Sun;
SunEcliptic.Axes = MJ2000Ec;

Create CoordinateSystem PropSatRef;
PropSatRef.Origin = PropSat;
PropSatRef.Axes = MJ2000Ec;

Create CoordinateSystem PhobosCentered;
PhobosCentered.Origin = Phobos;
PhobosCentered.Axes = MJ2000Eq;
%-----
%----- Subscribers
%-----

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames1;
OpenFrames1.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames1.UpperLeft = [ 0.04352941176470588 0.1284916201117318 ];
OpenFrames1.Size = [ 0.8458823529411764 0.7284916201117319 ];

```

```

OpenFrames1.RelativeZOrder = 105;
OpenFrames1.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames1.Add = {PropSat, Sun, Mars, Deimos, Phobos};
OpenFrames1.View = {NewView1};
OpenFrames1.CoordinateSystem = PropSatRef;
OpenFrames1.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawAxes = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawLabel = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawGrid = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames1.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames1.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames1.Axes = On;
OpenFrames1.AxesLength = 1;
OpenFrames1.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames1.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames1.XYPlane = Off;
OpenFrames1.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames1.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames1.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames1.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames1.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames1.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames1.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames1.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames1.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames1.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames1.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames1.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames1.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames1.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames1.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames1.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames1.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right', 'Top-Right'};

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames2;

```

```

OpenFrames2.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames2.UpperLeft = [ 0.1223529411764706 0.576536312849162 ];
OpenFrames2.Size = [ 0.851764705882353 0.4335195530726257 ];
OpenFrames2.RelativeZOrder = 114;
OpenFrames2.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames2.Add = {PropSat, Deimos, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OpenFrames2.View = {ToPhobos, ToDeimos};
OpenFrames2.CoordinateSystem = PropSatRef;
OpenFrames2.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawAxes = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawLabel = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawCenterPoint = [ true false false false true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawEndPoints = [ true false false false true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawGrid = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 1000 ];
OpenFrames2.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 20 ];
OpenFrames2.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 5 ];
OpenFrames2.Axes = Off;
OpenFrames2.AxesLength = 1;
OpenFrames2.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames2.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames2.XYPlane = Off;
OpenFrames2.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames2.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames2.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames2.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames2.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames2.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames2.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames2.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames2.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames2.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames2.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames2.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames2.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames2.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames2.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames2.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames2.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-

```

```

    Right', 'Top-Right');

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames3;
OpenFrames3.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames3.UpperLeft = [ 2.211764705882353 0.2480446927374302 ];
OpenFrames3.Size = [ 1.141176470588235 0.6893854748603352 ];
OpenFrames3.RelativeZOrder = 102;
OpenFrames3.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames3.Add = {PropSat, Mars, Phobos};
OpenFrames3.View = {CoordinateSystemView1};
OpenFrames3.CoordinateSystem = MarsMJ2000Eq;
OpenFrames3.DrawObject = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawAxes = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawLabel = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true ];
OpenFrames3.DrawVelocity = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawGrid = [ false false false ];
OpenFrames3.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames3.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames3.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames3.Axes = On;
OpenFrames3.AxesLength = 12756.2726;
OpenFrames3.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames3.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames3.XYPlane = On;
OpenFrames3.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames3.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames3.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames3.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames3.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames3.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames3.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames3.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames3.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames3.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames3.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames3.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames3.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames3.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;

```

```

OpenFrames3.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames3.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames3.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right'};

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames4;
OpenFrames4.SolverIterations = Current;

OpenFrames4.UpperLeft = [ 1.095882352941177 0 ];
OpenFrames4.Size = [ 1.095882352941177 1.062569832402235 ];
OpenFrames4.RelativeZOrder = 94;
OpenFrames4.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames4.Add = {PropSat, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OpenFrames4.View = {NewView1};
OpenFrames4.CoordinateSystem = EML2;
OpenFrames4.DrawObject = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawAxes = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawLabel = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true true ];
OpenFrames4.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawGrid = [ false false false false ];
OpenFrames4.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames4.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames4.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames4.Axes = On;
OpenFrames4.AxesLength = 12756.2726;
OpenFrames4.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames4.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames4.XYPlane = On;
OpenFrames4.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames4.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames4.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames4.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames4.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames4.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames4.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames4.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames4.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames4.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames4.ShowToolbar = true;

```

```

OpenFrames4.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames4.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames4.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames4.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames4.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames4.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right'};

Create ReportFile ReportFile1;
ReportFile1.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile1.UpperLeft = [ -19.39411764705882 0.1648706896551724 ];
ReportFile1.Size = [ 1.141176470588235 0.9741379310344828 ];
ReportFile1.RelativeZOrder = 88;
ReportFile1.Maximized = false;
ReportFile1.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-4.txt';
ReportFile1.Precision = 16;
ReportFile1.Add = {PropSat.UTCGregorian, PropSat.ElapsedSecs, PropSat.Sun.
    RMAG, PropSat.Mars.RMAG, PropSat.Phobos.RMAG, PropSat.Deimos.RMAG,
    PropSat.ToApo_ForceModel.Acceleration, PropSat.ToPeri_ForceModel.
    Acceleration, PropSat.FM.Acceleration, PropSat.PhobosCentered.VMAG};
ReportFile1.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile1.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile1.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile1.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile1.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile1.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile1.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile1.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create OrbitView OrbitView1;
OrbitView1.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView1.UpperLeft = [ 1.239411764705882 0 ];
OrbitView1.Size = [ 0.8852941176470588 0.9173184357541899 ];
OrbitView1.RelativeZOrder = 110;
OrbitView1.Maximized = false;
OrbitView1.Add = {PropSat, Deimos, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OrbitView1.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView1.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OrbitView1.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
OrbitView1.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView1.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView1.ShowPlot = true;

```

```

OrbitView1.MaxPlotPoints = 200000;
OrbitView1.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView1.ViewPointReference = SolarSystemBarycenter;
OrbitView1.ViewPointVector = [ 0 0 12000000000 ];
OrbitView1.ViewDirection = Sun;
OrbitView1.ViewScaleFactor = 0.05;
OrbitView1.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView1.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView1.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView1.XYPlane = Off;
OrbitView1.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView1.Axes = On;
OrbitView1.Grid = Off;
OrbitView1.SunLine = Off;
OrbitView1.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView1.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView1.EnableStars = On;
OrbitView1.EnableConstellations = Off;

Create XYPlot XYPlot1;
XYPlot1.SolverIterations = Current;
XYPlot1.UpperLeft = [ 1.081764705882353 0.7575418994413408 ];
XYPlot1.Size = [ 0.5035294117647059 0.4949720670391061 ];
XYPlot1.RelativeZOrder = 99;
XYPlot1.Maximized = false;
XYPlot1.XVariable = PropSat.ElapsedSecs;
XYPlot1.YVariables = {PropSat.Phobos.RMAG};
XYPlot1.ShowGrid = true;
XYPlot1.ShowPlot = true;

Create ReportFile coordinates;
coordinates.SolverIterations = Current;
coordinates.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
coordinates.Size = [ 0 0 ];
coordinates.RelativeZOrder = 0;
coordinates.Maximized = false;
coordinates.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-coordinates.txt';
coordinates.Precision = 16;
coordinates.Add = {PropSat.A1ModJulian, PropSat.SunEcliptic.X, PropSat.
    SunEcliptic.Y, PropSat.SunEcliptic.Z};
coordinates.WriteHeaders = true;
coordinates.LeftJustify = On;

```

```

coordinates.ZeroFill = Off;
coordinates.FixedWidth = true;
coordinates.Delimiter = ' ';
coordinates.ColumnWidth = 23;
coordinates.WriteReport = true;
coordinates.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile2;
ReportFile2.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile2.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile2.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile2.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile2.Maximized = false;
ReportFile2.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-earth.txt';
ReportFile2.Precision = 16;
ReportFile2.Add = {PropSat.A1ModJulian, Earth.SunEcliptic.X, Earth.
    SunEcliptic.Y, Earth.SunEcliptic.Z};
ReportFile2.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile2.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile2.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile2.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile2.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile2.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile2.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile2.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile3;
ReportFile3.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile3.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile3.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile3.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile3.Maximized = false;
ReportFile3.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-mars.txt';
ReportFile3.Precision = 16;
ReportFile3.Add = {PropSat.A1ModJulian, Mars.SunEcliptic.X, Mars.SunEcliptic.
    Y, Mars.SunEcliptic.Z};
ReportFile3.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile3.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile3.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile3.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile3.Delimiter = ' ';

```

```

ReportFile3.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile3.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile3.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile4;
ReportFile4.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile4.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile4.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile4.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile4.Maximized = false;
ReportFile4.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-phobos.txt';
ReportFile4.Precision = 16;
ReportFile4.Add = {PropSat.AlModJulian, Phobos.SunEcliptic.X, Phobos.
    SunEcliptic.Y, Phobos.SunEcliptic.Z};
ReportFile4.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile4.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile4.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile4.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile4.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile4.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile4.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile4.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create ReportFile ReportFile5;
ReportFile5.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile5.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile5.Size = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile5.RelativeZOrder = 0;
ReportFile5.Maximized = false;
ReportFile5.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\GMAT 2025a\
    sample2-3-deimos.txt';
ReportFile5.Precision = 16;
ReportFile5.Add = {PropSat.AlModJulian, Deimos.SunEcliptic.X, Deimos.
    SunEcliptic.Y, Deimos.SunEcliptic.Z};
ReportFile5.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile5.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile5.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile5.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile5.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile5.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile5.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile5.AppendToExistingFile = false;

```

```

Create OrbitView OrbitView2;
OrbitView2.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView2.UpperLeft = [ 0.298235294117647 0.0670391061452514 ];
OrbitView2.Size = [ 0.4994117647058823 0.4301675977653631 ];
OrbitView2.RelativeZOrder = 201;
OrbitView2.Maximized = false;
OrbitView2.Add = {PropSat, Mars, Phobos};
OrbitView2.CoordinateSystem = PhobosCentered;
OrbitView2.DrawObject = [ true true true ];
OrbitView2.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
OrbitView2.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView2.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView2.ShowPlot = true;
OrbitView2.MaxPlotPoints = 20000;
OrbitView2.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView2.ViewPointReference = Phobos;
OrbitView2.ViewPointVector = Phobos;
OrbitView2.ViewDirection = Phobos;
OrbitView2.ViewScaleFactor = 1;
OrbitView2.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = PhobosCentered;
OrbitView2.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView2.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView2.XYPlane = On;
OrbitView2.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView2.Axes = On;
OrbitView2.Grid = Off;
OrbitView2.SunLine = Off;
OrbitView2.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView2.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView2.EnableStars = On;
OrbitView2.EnableConstellations = On;

Create OrbitView OrbitView3;
OrbitView3.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView3.UpperLeft = [ 0.03470588235294118 0.5150837988826815 ];
OrbitView3.Size = [ 0.5 0.4670391061452514 ];
OrbitView3.RelativeZOrder = 121;
OrbitView3.Maximized = false;
OrbitView3.Add = {PropSat, Deimos, Mars, Phobos, Sun};
OrbitView3.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView3.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OrbitView3.DataCollectFrequency = 1;

```

```

OrbitView3.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView3.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView3.ShowPlot = true;
OrbitView3.MaxPlotPoints = 20000;
OrbitView3.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView3.ViewPointReference = SolarSystemBarycenter;
OrbitView3.ViewPointVector = [ 0 0 12000000000 ];
OrbitView3.ViewDirection = Sun;
OrbitView3.ViewScaleFactor = 0.05;
OrbitView3.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
OrbitView3.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView3.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView3.XYPlane = Off;
OrbitView3.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView3.Axes = On;
OrbitView3.Grid = Off;
OrbitView3.SunLine = Off;
OrbitView3.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView3.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView3.EnableStars = On;
OrbitView3.EnableConstellations = On;

%-----
%----- Arrays, Variables, Strings
%-----

Create Variable I;

%-----
%----- User Objects
%-----

Create OpenFramesView NewView1;
NewView1.ViewFrame = PropSat;
NewView1.ViewTrajectory = Off;
NewView1.InertialFrame = On;
NewView1.LookAtFrame = Mars;
NewView1.ShortestAngle = On;
NewView1.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
NewView1.SetCurrentLocation = On;
NewView1.CurrentEye = [ -65487.60096476031 -9132.715394198667
    42033.75601471769 ];
NewView1.CurrentCenter = [ -0.4300541023767437 -0.4356802623769909
    -0.8950808158551808 ];

```

```

NewView1.CurrentUp = [ -0.3365327431076686 0.8808559236822775
    -0.3329242474351631 ];
NewView1.FOVy = 45;

%-----
%----- User Objects
%-----

Create OpenFramesView CoordinateSystemView1;

CoordinateSystemView1.ViewFrame = PropSat;
CoordinateSystemView1.ViewTrajectory = Off;
CoordinateSystemView1.InertialFrame = On;
CoordinateSystemView1.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
CoordinateSystemView1.SetCurrentLocation = On;
CoordinateSystemView1.CurrentEye = [ 1850041031.404626 -1004383761.62577
    2547773627.111391 ];
CoordinateSystemView1.CurrentCenter = [ -0.4300539493560791
    -0.435680627822876 -0.89508056640625 ];
CoordinateSystemView1.CurrentUp = [ -0.7253426376049033 0.2701076349345477
    0.6331823778520901 ];
CoordinateSystemView1.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView ToPhobos;
ToPhobos.ViewFrame = PropSat;
ToPhobos.ViewTrajectory = On;
ToPhobos.InertialFrame = Off;
ToPhobos.LookAtFrame = Phobos;
ToPhobos.ShortestAngle = Off;
ToPhobos.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
ToPhobos.SetCurrentLocation = On;
ToPhobos.CurrentEye = [ -7.334825416444917 -55.27958669274469
    -70.43578093157312 ];
ToPhobos.CurrentCenter = [ -1.77635683940025e-15 7.105427357601002e-15 0 ];
ToPhobos.CurrentUp = [ -0.3699300896355834 -0.7117547815171055
    0.5971238228121092 ];
ToPhobos.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView ToDeimos;
ToDeimos.ViewFrame = PropSat;
ToDeimos.ViewTrajectory = On;
ToDeimos.InertialFrame = Off;
ToDeimos.LookAtFrame = Deimos;

```

```

ToDeimos.ShortestAngle = Off;
ToDeimos.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
ToDeimos.SetCurrentLocation = On;
ToDeimos.CurrentEye = [ 0 -10.40346197926335 0 ];
ToDeimos.CurrentCenter = [ 0 0 0 ];
ToDeimos.CurrentUp = [ 0 0 1 ];
ToDeimos.FOVy = 45;

%-----
%----- Mission Sequence
%-----

BeginMissionSequence;
Propagate 'ToPeri' ToPeri(PropSat) {PropSat.Sun.Periapsis, OrbitColor = [255
    128 64]};
For I = 1:1:6;
    Propagate 'ToApo' ToApo(PropSat) {PropSat.Sun.Apoapsis, OrbitColor = [0
        255 0]};
    Propagate 'ToPeri' ToPeri(PropSat) {PropSat.Sun.Periapsis, OrbitColor =
        [255 0 0]};
EndFor;
Propagate 'Mars' ToApo(PropSat) {PropSat.Mars.RMAG = 578000, OrbitColor =
    [255 0 128]};
Propagate 'Multibody' Prop(PropSat) {PropSat.Phobos.Periapsis, StopTolerance
    = 1e-10, OrbitColor = [255 128 255]};
Stop;

```

A.4 Aerobraking in the Martian Atmosphere

```

%-----
%----- User-Defined Celestial Bodies
%-----

Create Moon Phobos;
Phobos.NAIFId = 401;
Phobos.OrbitSpiceKernelName = {'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\mar085.
    bsp'};
Phobos.OrbitColor = [153 217 134];
Phobos.TargetColor = [154 213 125];
Phobos.EquatorialRadius = 13.5;
Phobos.Flattening = 0.3185185185185186;

```

```

Phobos.Mu = 0.00070934;
Phobos.PosVelSource = 'SPICE';
Phobos.CentralBody = 'Mars';
Phobos.RotationDataSource = 'IAUSimplified';
Phobos.OrientationEpoch = 21545;
Phobos.SpinAxisRAConstant = 0;
Phobos.SpinAxisRARate = -0.641;
Phobos.SpinAxisDECConstant = 90;
Phobos.SpinAxisDECRate = -0.5570000000000001;
Phobos.RotationConstant = 190.147;
Phobos.RotationRate = 360.9856235;
Phobos.TextureMapFileName = 'GenericCelestialBody.jpg';
Phobos.3DModelFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\Phobos_1_1000-2WFE
    .3ds';
Phobos.3DModelOffsetX = 0;
Phobos.3DModelOffsetY = 0;
Phobos.3DModelOffsetZ = 0;
Phobos.3DModelRotationX = 90;
Phobos.3DModelRotationY = 0;
Phobos.3DModelRotationZ = 0;
Phobos.3DModelScale = 1;

Create Moon Deimos;
Deimos.NAIFId = 402;
Deimos.OrbitSpiceKernelName = {'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\mar085.
    bsp'};
Deimos.OrbitColor = Tan;
Deimos.TargetColor = DarkGray;
Deimos.EquatorialRadius = 7.5;
Deimos.Flattening = 0.30666666666666666;
Deimos.Mu = 0.000158817;
Deimos.PosVelSource = 'SPICE';
Deimos.CentralBody = 'Mars';
Deimos.RotationDataSource = 'IAUSimplified';
Deimos.OrientationEpoch = 21545;
Deimos.SpinAxisRAConstant = 0;
Deimos.SpinAxisRARate = -0.641;
Deimos.SpinAxisDECConstant = 90;
Deimos.SpinAxisDECRate = -0.5570000000000001;
Deimos.RotationConstant = 190.147;
Deimos.RotationRate = 360.9856235;
Deimos.TextureMapFileName = 'GenericCelestialBody.jpg';
Deimos.3DModelFile = '';

```

```

Deimos.3DModelOffsetX = 0;
Deimos.3DModelOffsetY = 0;
Deimos.3DModelOffsetZ = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationX = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationY = 0;
Deimos.3DModelRotationZ = 0;
Deimos.3DModelScale = 10;

%-----
%----- Spacecraft
%-----

Create Spacecraft MarsSolarSailSC;
MarsSolarSailSC.DateFormat = UTCGregorian;
MarsSolarSailSC.Epoch = '09 May 2023 18:10:00.000';
MarsSolarSailSC.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
MarsSolarSailSC.DisplayStateType = Keplerian;
MarsSolarSailSC.SMA = 101919800.2251101;
MarsSolarSailSC.ECC = 0.5000000000000009;
MarsSolarSailSC.INC = 2.0444400000000015;
MarsSolarSailSC.RAAN = 25.46000000000203;
MarsSolarSailSC.AOP = 89.99500000000255;
MarsSolarSailSC.TA = 99.98914999999704;
MarsSolarSailSC.DryMass = 40;
MarsSolarSailSC.Cd = 2.2;
MarsSolarSailSC.Cr = 0.8;
MarsSolarSailSC.DragArea = 900;
MarsSolarSailSC.SRPArea = 900;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADDragScaleFactor = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADSRPScaleFactor = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.AtmosDensityScaleFactor = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.ExtendedMassPropertiesModel = 'None';

MarsSolarSailSC.NAIFId = -10001001;
MarsSolarSailSC.NAIFIdReferenceFrame = -9001001;
MarsSolarSailSC.OrbitColor = Red;
MarsSolarSailSC.TargetColor = Teal;
MarsSolarSailSC.OrbitErrorCovariance = [ 1e+70 0 0 0 0 0 ; 0 1e+70 0 0 0 0 ;
    0 0 1e+70 0 0 0 ; 0 0 0 1e+70 0 0 ; 0 0 0 0 1e+70 0 ; 0 0 0 0 0 1e+70 ];
MarsSolarSailSC.CdSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.CrSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.Id = 'SatId';
MarsSolarSailSC.Attitude = CoordinateSystemFixed;

```

```

MarsSolarSailSC.SPADSRPInterpolationMethod = Bilinear;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADSRPScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADDragInterpolationMethod = Bilinear;
MarsSolarSailSC.SPADDragScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;
MarsSolarSailSC.AtmosDensityScaleFactorSigma = 1e+70;

MarsSolarSailSC.ModelFile = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\Data\SolarSail-
concept2.3ds';
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelOffsetX = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelOffsetY = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelOffsetZ = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelRotationX = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelRotationY = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelRotationZ = 0;
MarsSolarSailSC.ModelScale = 1;
MarsSolarSailSC.AttitudeDisplayStateType = 'Quaternion';
MarsSolarSailSC.AttitudeRateDisplayStateType = 'AngularVelocity';
MarsSolarSailSC.AttitudeCoordinateSystem = EarthMJ2000Eq;
MarsSolarSailSC.EulerAngleSequence = '321';

%-----
%----- ForceModels
%-----

Create ForceModel MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.CentralBody = Mars;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.PrimaryBodies = {Mars};
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.SRP = Off;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.Degree = 4;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.Order = 4;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.StmLimit = 100;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.PotentialFile = 'Mars50c.cof
';
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.TideModel = 'None';
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.Drag.AtmosphereModel = TSExponentialAtmosphere
;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.Drag.F107 = 150;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.Drag.F107A = 150;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.Drag.MagneticIndex = 3;
MarsSOIPhobosDeimos_ForceModel.Drag.DragModel = 'Spherical';

```

```

%-----
%----- ForceModels
%-----

Create ForceModel ToApo_ForceModel;
ToApo_ForceModel.CentralBody = Sun;
ToApo_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune, Pluto
    , Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
ToApo_ForceModel.Drag = None;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP = On;
ToApo_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
ToApo_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.Flux = 1367;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;
ToApo_ForceModel.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;

Create ForceModel ToPeri_ForceModel;
ToPeri_ForceModel.CentralBody = Sun;
ToPeri_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune,
    Pluto, Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
ToPeri_ForceModel.Drag = None;
ToPeri_ForceModel.SRP = Off;
ToPeri_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
ToPeri_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;

Create ForceModel MarsSOI_ForceModel;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.CentralBody = Mars;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.PrimaryBodies = {Mars};
MarsSOI_ForceModel.PointMasses = {Earth, Jupiter, Luna, Mercury, Neptune,
    Saturn, Sun, Uranus, Venus};
MarsSOI_ForceModel.Drag = None;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.SRP = On;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.Degree = 4;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.Order = 4;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.StmLimit = 100;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.PotentialFile = 'Mars50c.cof';
MarsSOI_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.TideModel = 'None';
MarsSOI_ForceModel.SRP.Flux = 1367;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.SRP.SRPModel = Spherical;
MarsSOI_ForceModel.SRP.Nominal_Sun = 149597870.691;

```

```

Create ForceModel Propagator1_ForceModel;
Propagator1_ForceModel.CentralBody = Mars;
Propagator1_ForceModel.PrimaryBodies = {Mars};
Propagator1_ForceModel.SRP = Off;
Propagator1_ForceModel.RelativisticCorrection = Off;
Propagator1_ForceModel.ErrorControl = RSSStep;
Propagator1_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.Degree = 4;
Propagator1_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.Order = 4;
Propagator1_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.StmLimit = 100;
Propagator1_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.PotentialFile = 'Mars50c.cof';
Propagator1_ForceModel.GravityField.Mars.TideModel = 'None';
Propagator1_ForceModel.Drag.AtmosphereModel = TSExponentialAtmosphere;
Propagator1_ForceModel.Drag.F107 = 150;
Propagator1_ForceModel.Drag.F107A = 150;
Propagator1_ForceModel.Drag.MagneticIndex = 3;
Propagator1_ForceModel.Drag.DragModel = 'Spherical';

```

```

%-----
%----- Propagators
%-----

```

```

Create Propagator ToApo;
ToApo.FM = ToApo_ForceModel;
ToApo.Type = RungeKutta89;
ToApo.InitialStepSize = 60;
ToApo.Accuracy = 1e-14;
ToApo.MinStep = 21600;
ToApo.MaxStep = 21600;
ToApo.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
ToApo.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

```

```

Create Propagator ToPeri;
ToPeri.FM = ToPeri_ForceModel;
ToPeri.Type = RungeKutta89;
ToPeri.InitialStepSize = 60;
ToPeri.Accuracy = 1e-14;
ToPeri.MinStep = 21600;
ToPeri.MaxStep = 21600;
ToPeri.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
ToPeri.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

```

```

Create Propagator MarsSOI;

```

```

MarsSOI.FM = MarsSOI_ForceModel;
MarsSOI.Type = RungeKutta89;
MarsSOI.InitialStepSize = 60;
MarsSOI.Accuracy = 1e-15;
MarsSOI.MinStep = 1e-05;
MarsSOI.MaxStep = 2700;
MarsSOI.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
MarsSOI.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator MarsSOIphobosDeimos;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.FM = Propagator1_ForceModel;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.Type = PrinceDormand78;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.InitialStepSize = 60;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.Accuracy = 9.999999999999999e-12;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.MinStep = 1e-15;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.MaxStep = 1000;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
MarsSOIphobosDeimos.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator MarsForces;
MarsForces.FM = Propagator1_ForceModel;
MarsForces.Type = RungeKutta89;
MarsForces.InitialStepSize = 60;
MarsForces.Accuracy = 9.999999999999999e-12;
MarsForces.MinStep = 0.001;
MarsForces.MaxStep = 2700;
MarsForces.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
MarsForces.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

Create Propagator Propagator1;
Propagator1.FM = Propagator1_ForceModel;
Propagator1.Type = PrinceDormand78;
Propagator1.InitialStepSize = 60;
Propagator1.Accuracy = 9.999999999999999e-12;
Propagator1.MinStep = 1e-15;
Propagator1.MaxStep = 100;
Propagator1.MaxStepAttempts = 50;
Propagator1.StopIfAccuracyIsViolated = true;

%-----
%----- Coordinate Systems
%-----

```

```

Create CoordinateSystem SunEcliptic;
SunEcliptic.Origin = Sun;
SunEcliptic.Axes = MJ2000Ec;

Create CoordinateSystem MarsSolarSailSCRef;
MarsSolarSailSCRef.Origin = MarsSolarSailSC;
MarsSolarSailSCRef.Axes = MJ2000Ec;

Create CoordinateSystem MarsFixed;
MarsFixed.Origin = Mars;
MarsFixed.Axes = BodyFixed;

Create CoordinateSystem mj2000eqspc;
mj2000eqspc.Origin = Mars;
mj2000eqspc.Axes = MJ2000Eq;

%-----
%----- Subscribers
%-----

Create OrbitView DefaultOrbitView;
DefaultOrbitView.SolverIterations = Current;
DefaultOrbitView.UpperLeft = [ 0.2658823529411765 0.01876955161626695 ];
DefaultOrbitView.Size = [ 0.2782352941176471 0.5620437956204379 ];
DefaultOrbitView.RelativeZOrder = 34;
DefaultOrbitView.Maximized = false;
DefaultOrbitView.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Mars, Sun, Deimos, Phobos};
DefaultOrbitView.CoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
DefaultOrbitView.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
DefaultOrbitView.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
DefaultOrbitView.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
DefaultOrbitView.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
DefaultOrbitView.ShowPlot = true;
DefaultOrbitView.MaxPlotPoints = 20000;
DefaultOrbitView.ShowLabels = true;
DefaultOrbitView.ViewPointReference = SolarSystemBarycenter;
DefaultOrbitView.ViewPointVector = [ 0 0 12000000000 ];
DefaultOrbitView.ViewDirection = Sun;
DefaultOrbitView.ViewScaleFactor = 0.05;
DefaultOrbitView.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = SunEcliptic;
DefaultOrbitView.ViewUpAxis = Z;
DefaultOrbitView.EclipticPlane = Off;
DefaultOrbitView.XYPlane = Off;

```

```

DefaultOrbitView.WireFrame = Off;
DefaultOrbitView.Axes = On;
DefaultOrbitView.Grid = Off;
DefaultOrbitView.SunLine = Off;
DefaultOrbitView.UseInitialView = On;
DefaultOrbitView.StarCount = 7000;
DefaultOrbitView.EnableStars = On;
DefaultOrbitView.EnableConstellations = Off;

Create ReportFile ReportFile1;
ReportFile1.SolverIterations = Current;
ReportFile1.UpperLeft = [ 0 0 ];
ReportFile1.Size = [ 0.7394117647058823 0.5067778936392076 ];
ReportFile1.RelativeZOrder = 947;
ReportFile1.Maximized = false;
ReportFile1.Filename = 'C:\Users\ozgeo\Desktop\FENG-498\GMAT\
    AtmosphereExperiments\mars-aerobrake-report1.txt';
ReportFile1.Precision = 16;
ReportFile1.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC.UTCGregorian, MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs,
    MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.
    Phobos.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.Deimos.RMAG, MarsSolarSailSC.
    ToApo_ForceModel.Acceleration, MarsSolarSailSC.ToPeri_ForceModel.
    Acceleration, MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.Altitude, MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.
    VelPeriaapsis, MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.VelApoapsis};
ReportFile1.WriteHeaders = true;
ReportFile1.LeftJustify = On;
ReportFile1.ZeroFill = Off;
ReportFile1.FixedWidth = true;
ReportFile1.Delimiter = ' ';
ReportFile1.ColumnWidth = 23;
ReportFile1.WriteReport = true;
ReportFile1.AppendToExistingFile = false;

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames1;
OpenFrames1.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames1.UpperLeft = [ 0.008823529411764706 0.5349322210636079 ];
OpenFrames1.Size = [ 0.3076470588235294 0.5359749739311783 ];
OpenFrames1.RelativeZOrder = 37;
OpenFrames1.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames1.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Sun, Mars, Deimos, Phobos};
OpenFrames1.View = {NewView1};
OpenFrames1.CoordinateSystem = MarsSolarSailSCRef;
OpenFrames1.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];

```

```

OpenFrames1.DrawTrajectory = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawAxes = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawLabel = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames1.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawGrid = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames1.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 2 ];
OpenFrames1.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 10 ];
OpenFrames1.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 14 ];
OpenFrames1.Axes = On;
OpenFrames1.AxesLength = 1;
OpenFrames1.AxesLabels = On;
OpenFrames1.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames1.XYPlane = Off;
OpenFrames1.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames1.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames1.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames1.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames1.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames1.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames1.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames1.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames1.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames1.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames1.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames1.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames1.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames1.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames1.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames1.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames1.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right', 'Top-Right'};

Create OpenFramesInterface OpenFrames2;
OpenFrames2.SolverIterations = Current;
OpenFrames2.UpperLeft = [ 0 0.01876955161626695 ];
OpenFrames2.Size = [ 0.2658823529411765 0.5359749739311783 ];
OpenFrames2.RelativeZOrder = 45;
OpenFrames2.Maximized = false;
OpenFrames2.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Mars, Sun, Deimos, Phobos};

```

```

OpenFrames2.View = {ToPhobos, ToDeimos, NewView2};
OpenFrames2.CoordinateSystem = MarsSolarSailSCRef;
OpenFrames2.DrawObject = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawTrajectory = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawAxes = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawXYPlane = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawLabel = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawUsePropLabel = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawCenterPoint = [ true true true true true ];
OpenFrames2.DrawEndPoints = [ true true true true false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawVelocity = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawGrid = [ false false false false false ];
OpenFrames2.DrawLineWidth = [ 2 2 2 2 1000 ];
OpenFrames2.DrawMarkerSize = [ 10 10 10 10 20 ];
OpenFrames2.DrawFontSize = [ 14 14 14 14 5 ];
OpenFrames2.Axes = Off;
OpenFrames2.AxesLength = 1;
OpenFrames2.AxesLabels = Off;
OpenFrames2.FrameLabel = Off;
OpenFrames2.XYPlane = Off;
OpenFrames2.EclipticPlane = Off;
OpenFrames2.EnableStars = On;
OpenFrames2.StarCatalog = 'inp_StarsHYGv3.txt';
OpenFrames2.StarCount = 40000;
OpenFrames2.MinStarMag = -2;
OpenFrames2.MaxStarMag = 6;
OpenFrames2.MinStarPixels = 1;
OpenFrames2.MaxStarPixels = 10;
OpenFrames2.MinStarDimRatio = 0.5;
OpenFrames2.ShowPlot = true;
OpenFrames2.ShowToolbar = true;
OpenFrames2.SolverIterLastN = 1;
OpenFrames2.ShowVR = false;
OpenFrames2.PlaybackTimeScale = 3600;
OpenFrames2.MultisampleAntiAliasing = On;
OpenFrames2.MSAASamples = 2;
OpenFrames2.DrawFontPosition = {'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-Right', 'Top-
    Right', 'Bottom-Right'};

Create XYPlot SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot;
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.SolverIterations = Current;
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.UpperLeft = [ 0.5435294117647059 0.01876955161626695 ];
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.Size = [ 0.2782352941176471 0.5620437956204379 ];

```

```

SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.RelativeZOrder = 29;
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.Maximized = false;
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.XVariable = MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs;
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.YVariables = {MarsSolarSailSC.Phobos.RMAG};
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.ShowGrid = true;
SCPhobosRMAGTimePlot.ShowPlot = true;

Create XYPlot SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs;
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.SolverIterations = Current;
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.UpperLeft = [ 0.2658823529411765 0.5547445255474452
];
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.Size = [ 0.2782352941176471 0.5620437956204379 ];
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.RelativeZOrder = 42;
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.Maximized = false;
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.XVariable = MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs;
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.YVariables = {MarsSolarSailSC.EarthMJ2000Eq.VMAG};
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.ShowGrid = true;
SCVMAGEarthvElapsedSecs.ShowPlot = true;

Create XYPlot SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs;
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.SolverIterations = Current;
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.UpperLeft = [ 0.821764705882353 0.5547445255474452 ];
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.Size = [ 0.2782352941176471 0.5620437956204379 ];
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.RelativeZOrder = 14;
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.Maximized = false;
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.XVariable = MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs;
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.YVariables = {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.RMAG};
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.ShowGrid = true;
SCRMAGSunvEalpsedSecs.ShowPlot = true;

Create XYPlot XYPlot1;
XYPlot1.SolverIterations = Current;
XYPlot1.UpperLeft = [ 0.821764705882353 0.01876955161626695 ];
XYPlot1.Size = [ 0.2782352941176471 0.5620437956204379 ];
XYPlot1.RelativeZOrder = 19;
XYPlot1.Maximized = false;
XYPlot1.XVariable = MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs;
XYPlot1.YVariables = {MarsSolarSailSC.SunEcliptic.VMAG};
XYPlot1.ShowGrid = true;
XYPlot1.ShowPlot = true;

Create XYPlot XYPlot2;
XYPlot2.SolverIterations = Current;

```

```

XYPlot2.UpperLeft = [ 0.5435294117647059 0.5547445255474452 ];
XYPlot2.Size = [ 0.2782352941176471 0.5620437956204379 ];
XYPlot2.RelativeZOrder = 24;
XYPlot2.Maximized = false;
XYPlot2.XVariable = MarsSolarSailSC.ElapsedSecs;
XYPlot2.YVariables = {MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.Altitude};
XYPlot2.ShowGrid = true;
XYPlot2.ShowPlot = true;

Create OrbitView OrbitView1;
OrbitView1.SolverIterations = Current;
OrbitView1.UpperLeft = [ 0.4470588235294118 0.001042752867570386 ];
OrbitView1.Size = [ 0.5 1.008342022940563 ];
OrbitView1.RelativeZOrder = 940;
OrbitView1.Maximized = false;
OrbitView1.Add = {MarsSolarSailSC, Mars, Phobos};
OrbitView1.CoordinateSystem = mj2000eqspc;
OrbitView1.DrawObject = [ true true true ];
OrbitView1.DataCollectFrequency = 1;
OrbitView1.UpdatePlotFrequency = 50;
OrbitView1.NumPointsToRedraw = 0;
OrbitView1.ShowPlot = true;
OrbitView1.MaxPlotPoints = 1000;
OrbitView1.ShowLabels = true;
OrbitView1.ViewPointReference = Mars;
OrbitView1.ViewPointVector = [ 0 0 30000 ];
OrbitView1.ViewDirection = Mars;
OrbitView1.ViewScaleFactor = 1;
OrbitView1.ViewUpCoordinateSystem = mj2000eqspc;
OrbitView1.ViewUpAxis = Z;
OrbitView1.EclipticPlane = Off;
OrbitView1.XYPlane = On;
OrbitView1.WireFrame = Off;
OrbitView1.Axes = Off;
OrbitView1.Grid = Off;
OrbitView1.SunLine = Off;
OrbitView1.UseInitialView = On;
OrbitView1.StarCount = 7000;
OrbitView1.EnableStars = Off;
OrbitView1.EnableConstellations = Off;

%-----
%----- Arrays, Variables, Strings

```

```

%-----
Create Variable I;

%-----
%----- User Objects
%-----

Create OpenFramesView NewView1;
NewView1.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
NewView1.ViewTrajectory = Off;
NewView1.InertialFrame = On;
NewView1.LookAtFrame = Mars;
NewView1.ShortestAngle = On;
NewView1.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
NewView1.SetCurrentLocation = On;
NewView1.CurrentEye = [ 9479.037101902697 5934.445309173406 -4358.77263613585
    ];
NewView1.CurrentCenter = [ -1.818989403545856e-12 9.094947017729282e-13
    -1.818989403545856e-12 ];
NewView1.CurrentUp = [ 0.03740204807163172 -0.6296736383506438
    -0.7759588880645093 ];
NewView1.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView ToPhobos;
ToPhobos.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
ToPhobos.ViewTrajectory = On;
ToPhobos.InertialFrame = Off;
ToPhobos.LookAtFrame = Phobos;
ToPhobos.ShortestAngle = Off;
ToPhobos.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
ToPhobos.SetCurrentLocation = On;
ToPhobos.CurrentEye = [ 1.899751414380965 -0.2706040898648264
    -1.773737773303898 ];
ToPhobos.CurrentCenter = [ -1.110223024625157e-15 0 4.440892098500626e-16 ];
ToPhobos.CurrentUp = [ -0.05703653453164897 0.9760374949040735
    -0.2099943862821115 ];
ToPhobos.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView ToDeimos;
ToDeimos.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
ToDeimos.ViewTrajectory = On;
ToDeimos.InertialFrame = Off;
ToDeimos.LookAtFrame = Deimos;

```

```

ToDeimos.ShortestAngle = Off;
ToDeimos.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
ToDeimos.SetCurrentLocation = On;
ToDeimos.CurrentEye = [ 0 -10.40346197926335 0 ];
ToDeimos.CurrentCenter = [ 0 0 0 ];
ToDeimos.CurrentUp = [ 0 0 1 ];
ToDeimos.FOVy = 45;

Create OpenFramesView NewView2;
NewView2.ViewFrame = MarsSolarSailSC;
NewView2.ViewTrajectory = Off;
NewView2.InertialFrame = Off;
NewView2.LookAtFrame = Mars;
NewView2.ShortestAngle = Off;
NewView2.SetDefaultLocation = Off;
NewView2.SetCurrentLocation = On;
NewView2.CurrentEye = [ 0 -3.336397647857666 0 ];
NewView2.CurrentCenter = [ 0 0 0 ];
NewView2.CurrentUp = [ 0 0 1 ];
NewView2.FOVy = 45;

%-----
%----- Mission Sequence
%-----

BeginMissionSequence;
Propagate 'ToPeri' ToPeri(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.Periapsis,
    OrbitColor = [255 128 64]};
For I = 1:1:6;
    Propagate 'ToApo' ToApo(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.Apoapsis,
        OrbitColor = [0 255 0]};
    Propagate 'ToPeri' ToPeri(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Sun.Periapsis
        };
EndFor;
Propagate 'ToMarsSOI' ToApo(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.RMAG =
    578000, OrbitColor = [255 0 128]};
Propagate 'ToPhobosFlyby' MarsSOI(PhobosDeimos(MarsSolarSailSC) {
    MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.Altitude = 61, StopTolerance = 1e-10, OrbitColor =
    [255 128 255]};
Propagate Propagator1(MarsSolarSailSC) {MarsSolarSailSC.Mars.Apoapsis,
    OrbitColor = [128 255 255]};
Stop;

```